

MATH40000: Fourth Year Research Project

Modelling Pollen Tube Growth in Electromagnetic Fields

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Abstract

Pollen tubes are crucial for the successful reproduction of flowering plants, facilitating the secure transfer of male gametes to the female reproductive organs, leading to fertilization and the formation of seeds. This process is essential for enhancing the genetic diversity of plants and therefore underpins the stability of entire ecosystems. Incorporating an understanding of a pollen tube's complex tissue structure with the multitude of factors that regulate growth presents an intricate and multi-scale modelling problem. We use fluid dynamics and molecular transport to shed light on how some of these growth mechanisms may be influenced by external factors such as electromagnetic fields. We employ an analytical approach to model fluid flow in the shank of a pollen tube and compare the results with other approaches. Our model outlines how features such as pressure gradients and growth speed can influence fluid flow in the shank. In addition, we are able to attribute pollen tube's oriented growth in electromagnetic fields, in part, to a changing distribution of free Ca^{2+} in the tip, something which has thus far been unclear. The development of accurate and predictive models for pollen tube growth is essential for gaining insight into the fundamental processes underlying plant reproduction and can have applications in agriculture, plant breeding, and biotechnology.

Glossary

actin filaments provide mechanical support, determine cell shape, and allow movement of the cell surface, thereby enabling cells to migrate, engulf particles, and divide.

anther the part of the male part of the plant that contains the pollen.

ATPase an enzyme that catalyses a dephosphorylation reaction which releases energy.

callose a plant polysaccharide.

callose plugs block off the older parts of the tube and maintain the cytoplasm near the growing tip.

cell membrane the semipermeable membrane surrounding the insides a cell.

cell wall a rigid layer lying outside the cell membrane of the cells.

cellulose microfibrils a very fine fibre-like strand containing cellulose.

cytoplasm a thick solution that fills each cell and is enclosed by the cell membranes.

cytoskeleton a microscopic network of protein filaments and tubules in the cytoplasm of many living cells, giving them shape and coherence.

endocytosis a cellular process in which substances are brought into the cell.

exocytosis a process by which the contents of a cell vacuole are released to the exterior through fusion of the vacuole membrane with the cell membrane.

gametes a reproductive cell of an animal or plant.

germinate begin to grow and put out shoots after a period of dormancy.

Golgi a complex of vesicles and folded membranes within the cytoplasm of most eukaryotic cells, involved in secretion and intracellular transport.

microtubules involved in mitosis, cell motility, intracellular transport, and maintenance of cell shape.

mitochondria organelles found in large numbers in most cells, in which the biochemical processes of respiration and energy production occur.

myosin a fibrous protein involved in the motion of a cell.

nucleus the membrane-enclosed organelle within a cell that contains the chromosomes.

ovule the part of the ovary of seed plants that contains the female germ cell and after fertilization becomes the seed.

pectin a group of substances which forms gels when dissolved in water under suitable conditions.

permanent vacuoles a large, membrane-bound structure that primarily serves as a storage area for water and dissolved substances such as ions, sugars, and waste products.

pollen grain each of the microscopic particles, typically single cells, of which pollen is composed.

pollen tube a hollow tube which develops from a pollen grain.

pollination the act of transferring pollen from the male part of the plant to the female part.

rough endoplasmic reticulum produces proteins for the rest of the cell to function.

stigma the female part of the plant that receives the pollen.

style a narrow, typically elongated extension of the ovary, bearing the stigma.

transport vesicles block off the older parts of the tube and maintain the cytoplasm near the growing tip.

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1 Introduction and Literature Review

1.1 Motivation

The growth of pollen tubes (see Figure 1(a)) plays a pivotal role in a plant's life cycle owing to their ability to transfer genetic information from one plant to another. The development of these cells is a key driving factor in the diversification of the genetic makeup of plant species, a process that communities around the world are reliant on. Pollen tubes are attractive to model because their finger-like structures (which are also shared with fungi, root hairs and some bacteria) have relatively simple geometries making them the building blocks of knowledge when trying to understand the dynamics of more complex cells. In addition, their ease of culturing and rapid growth has meant that many features of their growth have been studied meticulously over multiple decades [27]. However, despite the richness of data in this field, many mechanisms of pollen tube growth are still not yet fully understood. The governing factors are often interlinked, making models combining them extremely complex and difficult to interpret. To tackle the complexity of the problem, a multitude of mathematical tools can be implemented such as a statistical analysis of results in combination with analytical or numerical model formulations to help explain features of the results. With an increasing demand for crop production to feed a growing population and unparalleled declines in insect pollinators, the threat to food security has never been greater. A more sophisticated understanding of plants (especially the mechanisms through which they reproduce) is therefore required more than ever to manage this threat as best as possible and avoid a potential crisis.

1.2 Biological Background of Pollen Tubes

Like animals, plants have male and female gametes. The male gametes (sperm cells) are stored in pollen grains, which are responsible for transporting the sperm cells to the female gametes (eggs). In order to leave the confines of the parent plant, pollen grains can be found on an exposed part of the plant, the anther, as can be seen in Figure 1 (a). These pollen grains are then transported to a foreign plant by the wind or animals (or water for water borne plants) in a process known as pollination. Most pollen grains never reach another plant let alone another stigma, the entry to the female part of the plant. If the pollen grain is compatible with such a stigma, it begins to germinate, forming a tubular protuberance known as a pollen tube. The pollen tube keeps extending, via tip growth, down the style of the plant, which forms a path to the eggs. On reaching the ovule, the housing for the eggs, the pollen tube explodes, releasing the two sperm cells which can then fertilise the egg [28]. The structure of this mechanism can be seen in Figure 1 (a).

Figure 1: (a) Diagram of a typical plant with the key reproductive organs labelled. Reproduced from [56]. (b) Internal Structure of a Pollen cell. Reproduced from [3].

The internal structure of a pollen cell is similar to a typical plant cell (see Figure 1 (b)). It has a boundary formed by a cell membrane (which regulates the influx and outflow of materials in and out of the cell) and cell wall (that provides structural support to the cell) [40]. The membrane bound organelles are suspended in cytoplasm, a jelly-like substance that contains water, salts and various organic materials that add to the cells support system and provides a medium through which solutes can be transported. The main way a pollen cell maintains its structure is through its permanent vacuoles which store water and are essential in supplying the hydrostatic pressure required to promote cell growth. Like all cells, the pollen cell has a nucleus that stores the DNA of the cell and mitochondria which are responsible for respiration, releasing all the energy the cell needs to fulfill its function. On the other hand, the pollen cell is rather unique in that it stores within itself more cells, namely the two sperm cells. The development of the cell is centered around the tip of the pollen tube, sometimes known as the apical region. In order to concentrate the important organelles there, periodic callose plugs are formed as the pollen tube grows [49].

The cell wall expansion is managed by adding soft wall material which allows the hydrostatic pressure to stretch the cell wall [40]. These new materials are delivered to the boundary of the cell via transport vesicles, small spherical membrane- bound organelles. Golgi and rough endoplasmic reticulum combine to synthesise the proteins necessary to form these materials and package them into the transport vesicles. The actin filaments and microtubules are rod like structures arranged along the length of the cell that make up the cytoskeleton

which forms the "backbone" of the cell (see Figure 2 (A)). They give the cell structural support as well as acting as rails, allowing intracellular transport of other organelles such as the transport vesicles [31].

Vesicles are transported along the tracks of the cytoskeleton with the help of myosin. Myosin is a protein capable of converting chemical energy into mechanical energy and is therefore responsible for generating the force and movement necessary for organelle transport. Myosin comes in a variety of forms, each with their own role, some of which are still not yet fully understood like that of myosin-8 which interacts between the cell membrane and the actin filaments, effectively shifting the transport rails [29]. Myosin-11 is the form responsible for moving organelles such as the vesicles along the the actin. The positioning and orientation of actin is therefore a key aspect in explaining how the vesicles are transported through the cell.

The actin filaments are usually aligned parallel to the direction of movement of the pollen tube [39]. The exchange of substances between the vesicles and the cell wall at the tip of the cell mean that the vesicles are constantly moving back and forth along the length of the cell. Consequently, there must be actin filaments that allow for movement down the cell as well those that can transport organelles back up the cell. The two roles are spatially split between the centre of the cell and the outer edge of the cell. Interestingly, which way round this occurs is species dependent; angiosperms, who make up 80% of the plant species, typically have vesicles moving toward the tip in the outer

Figure 2: (A) Diagram of the actin arrangement in a pollen tube causing the cone-shaped distribution of vesicles in the tip as well as the formation of calcium crosslinks with pectin in the cell wall. (B) Illustration of calcium being absorbed through calcium channels and how the calcium channels are most active at the apex of the tip and less active down the sides of the tip. Both reproduced from [3].

part of the cell whilst gymnosperms usually have tip-bound vesicles moving in the centre of the cell [31]. The tip of the cell is sometimes known as the "clear zone" as it is almost exclusively filled with the minuscule vesicles. Actin and other larger organelles are excluded from this region. As a result, beyond the actin fringe, the movement of vesicles is generally considered to be primarily governed by diffusion and convection [31]. This helps explain why the vesicles form a fountain or cone shape at the tip [58] as can be seen in Figure 2 (A).

The mechanism in which myosin releases actin is controlled by the concentration of Ca^{2+} which inhibits both the motile activity and the actin-stimulated ATPase (an enzyme that governs the gripping and releasing of myosin to actin) activity of this myosin [57]. The function of calcium is then two-fold in its effect on the vesicles as it is also thought to be responsible for promoting the fusion of vesicles to the cell membrane in a process known as exocytosis [32]. Free Ca^{2+} are themselves taken in by the tip of the cell through endocytosis in the calcium channels (as can be seen in Figure 2 (B)) which can explain the steep concentration gradient of Ca^{2+} typically observed at the tip of the cell [33]. The vesicles themselves contain many substances such as pectin, the main component of the cell wall, as well as cellulose microfibrils and callose which reinforce the wall in mature parts of the cell. The pectin secreted by the vesicles comes mostly in the form Methylsterified pectin, which softens the wall locally upon its deposition. The enzyme pectin methylsterase (PME), which is found in the cell wall, then acts as a catalyst for the chemical reaction that the pectin undergoes. The demethylsterified pectin that is produced from this reaction has the capability of forming calcium crosslinks with the Ca^{2+} present in the cell wall, which strengthens the local wall considerably [45] (a diagram of this can be seen in Figure 2 (A)). The distribution of the PMEs and their inhibitors (PMEIs), of which pH is thought to one, is therefore crucial in determining the mechanisms of growth [17].

1.3 Macro and Micro Mechanics of Pollen Tube Growth

1.3.1 Empirical Growth Rates

Before we derive any theoretical models, it would be helpful to study some data representing the growth. After data is collected and analysed, empirical models can be developed whose soul purpose is to represent the observed data. The work done by Jefferies, which primarily concerned itself with growth rates, gives insight into how the first models for pollen tube growth were formulated [27].

Jefferies measured the length of multiple apple pollen tubes at regular time intervals and plotted them as can be seen in Figure 3. On noticing the logistic-like development of the pollen tubes' length, he initially proposed that the

growth of the pollen tube can be modelled by:

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = rL \left(1 - \frac{L}{K}\right), \quad (1.1)$$

where L is the length of the tube, t is time, and r and K are parameters of the model whose interpretations are discussed below. The logistic growth model is well known and widely used as a basic model for many Biological systems. The solution to (1.1) can be shown to be

$$L = \frac{K}{Ae^{-tr} + 1}, \quad (1.2)$$

where A is some constant can be determined by the initial length. Thus, (1.2) can be rewritten as

$$L = \frac{K}{\left(\frac{K-L_0}{L_0}\right)e^{-tr} + 1}, \quad (1.3)$$

where L_0 is the initial length. Details of this derivation can be found in Appendix 5.1.

(1.1) suggests that the system has two equilibria (where $\frac{dL}{dt} = 0$): $L = 0$ (unstable) and $L = K$ (stable). The stability of the second equilibrium suggests that K is the maximum length that the pollen tube can reach. It should be noted that the logistic growth model breaks down if $L(t = 0) = 0$. In addition, for $L \ll K$, $\frac{dL}{dt} \approx rL$ which indicates that initially the cell grows exponentially at a rate r . This gives us a physical interpretation of what the parameters K and r represent in the logistic Equation.

Jefferies noticed that his results (again in Figure 3) had a slight asymmetry about their peak growth rate which the logistic growth model couldn't account for. In light of this, he opted for using a similar model, Gompertz growth, which could account for these asymmetries [27]. The Gompertz growth model obeys

Figure 3: Jefferies' graph of observed lengths of pollen tubes through time as well as a fitted curve. Data and graph reproduced from [27].

the following differential equation:

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = r \ln \left(\frac{K}{L} \right) L \quad (1.4)$$

which can be verified to explicitly follow (details in Appendix 5.2):

$$L = Ke^{-be^{-rt}} \quad (1.5)$$

where b represents a delay term. Looking at the equilibria of equation 1.4, we see that $L = K$ is the stable equilibrium and so K again represents the terminal length of the pollen tube. Since equation 1.4 can be rewritten as $\frac{dL}{dt} = r(L \ln K - L \ln L)$ and noting that L will dominate $\ln L$ for small L we see that $\frac{dL}{dt} \approx rL \ln K$ for small L . This means, r represents the rate of exponential growth that the pollen tube initially undergoes (this time relative to K). The additional parameter is b , which shifts the graph horizontally and can therefore represent a delay in germination of the pollen tube. Such a b could easily be included within the logistic model but the notation is slightly nicer for the Gompertz function and is only included to illustrate the ease in which a delay can be included in such a model. We will compare the suitability of both of these models in more detail later (Section 2.1.1).

These models provide us with a very broad understanding of what is going on when the pollen tubes grow. They are able to capture key features of pollen tube growth like terminal lengths and in some cases asymmetries in growth rates and delays in germination. However, the empirical nature of these models means they have clear limitations in that they fail to describe how the key factors affecting growth actually influence growth. This ultimately means that we have to employ extreme caution using their predicative capabilities. Instead, they should really only be used to give us a general idea of the timescales of pollen tube growth and possibly an intuition about how some of the features might interact such as a slowing of growth rates as the tube approaches its terminal length.

1.3.2 Pressure and Cell Wall Mechanics

It has been observed that internal pressures within the pollen tube can reach 1 MPa [2] (equivalent to 100m depth pressure in water) and that fluctuations in osmolarity (which affects water uptake and therefore internal pressure) induces variations in growth rates [31]. For this reason, the pressure difference between the cell and its surroundings is considered the driving force of cell growth. Therefore, understanding how pressure impacts cell expansion is pivotal into modelling pollen tube growth. One of the most instrumental modelling developments for plant cells came from Lockhart. He coupled the internal pressure of the cell with the cell wall mechanics to model cell growth [38]. As we discussed in the previous section, pollen tubes typically exhibit growth rates

that drop off as they approach their terminal length. Lockhart is able to capture this phenomena by introducing a term he calls extensibility, ϕ , which is a measure of the cell wall’s ability to regulate the cell’s size under a given stress. It is therefore intuitive that ϕ will be a function of the properties of the cell wall. An additional observation that has been fairly well established is that pollen tubes cease to grow when the internal pressure is reduced below a critical value [27]. Lockhart deems this critical value the yield stress Y . In Lockhart’s derivation, he also assumed that cells behave as linear viscoplastic elements, i.e. a body that exhibits both viscous flow-like and plastic (permanently deformed) behaviour. He further assumes that the cell has the capacity to regulate pressure within the cell via osmosis. If l is the length of the cell, P is the pressure in the cell, Y is the yield stress and ϕ is extensibility then Lockhart’s equation can be expressed as a Bingham-type law:

$$\frac{1}{l} \frac{dl}{dt} = \phi(P - Y) \quad \text{for } P > Y. \quad (2.1)$$

Lockhart’s equation captures the plastic behaviour of the pollen tube and therefore represents a creeping nature of the cell as a result of the plastic deformation of the cell wall. The pressure P is a combination of hydrostatic pressure (the pressure exerted by a fluid at rest) in the cell as well as the difference in osmotic pressure (due to the movement of water through osmosis) and is, in principal, a function of time as well. However, as cells are able to regulate their osmotic potential (and therefore their pressure) in a matter of seconds [59] (which is much smaller than the timescale of growth) pressure is often assumed to be constant.

Lockhart’s model acts as backbone for the development of other theoretical growth models involving Pressure. An example of an extension of Lockhart’s model could be that of Ortega’s [42] who allows pressure to vary with time. Models that don’t assume constant pressure will usually include an elastic term which takes the form $\frac{1}{l} \frac{dl}{dt} \propto \frac{dP}{dt}$ leading to

$$\frac{1}{l} \frac{dl}{dt} = \underbrace{\phi(P - Y)}_{\text{plastic growth}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{E} \frac{dP}{dt}}_{\text{elastic deformation}}, \quad (2.2)$$

where E is the Young modulus of the cell wall material. We can see that elastic term will only be non-zero when pressure isn’t constant and so if the pressure is constant we recover Lockhart’s equation. As previously mentioned, the timescale of osmotic regulation in comparison to growth means pressure is usually assumed to be constant and so a more common way to develop Lockhart’s model is done by analysing the micro-mechanics of the cell wall to uncover the form of ϕ in terms of the properties of the cell wall. One of the more prominent approaches was done by Dyson and Jensen who considered how different orientations of the fibres within the cell wall could effect the extensibility [16]. They considered multiple cases, the most straightforward being when the fibres

were perpendicular to the axial length and remained that way through growth. A schematic of this case is given in Figure 4.

They considered the limiting case when the length of the fibres remained constant which can be interpreted as the assumption that the thickness of the cell wall didn't change. They also assumed that any new fibres added were also done so perpendicular to the axial length which would mean that the density of the cell wall remained homogeneous. In addition to some other assumptions, it was assumed that the centreline of the cell remained straight during growth. Under this set of assumptions, Dyson and Jensen were able to derive an ODE which describes the dynamics of the pollen tube of radius R and cell wall thickness h :

$$\frac{dl}{dt} = \frac{R(P - Y)}{8h} \int_0^l \frac{1}{\mu} dx, \quad (2.3)$$

where x parameterises the axial length of the pollen tube and the quantity μ quantifies the 'viscosity matrix'. The matrix viscosity was a parameter that depended on the local fibre density and was a representation of the fluid's resistance to axial flow whose form was derived by considering a stress tensor that satisfied their required conditions. Comparing (2.3) to Lockhart's model, we have that the extensibility is given by

$$\phi = \frac{R}{8h} \left[\frac{1}{l} \int_0^l \frac{1}{\mu} dx \right], \quad (2.4)$$

i.e. the average inverse viscosity which has been scaled for a suitable geometry. Dyson and Jensen then go on to examine the cases for different fibre configurations in the cell wall.

The consideration of different orientations of fibres in the cell allowed Dyson and Jensen to explain a change in extensibility in terms of a change in orientation of the fibres. This uncovers a major mechanism in which pollen tubes are able to regulate their growth rate. To use their model to approximate growth rate evolutions for different fibre orientations we would need to know the numerical values for each of the relevant parameters. Unfortunately, there is very limited data on the required viscosity μ and the best we can currently do is approximate the order of such parameters. If more data were to be collected, we could get a proper idea of the range of values the parameter takes and in doing so strengthen existing models.

Figure 4: A schematic of the case Dyson and Jensen consider when the fibres on the cell wall are perpendicular to the axial length. Here, P is the pressure difference, Y is the yield stress, E is the young modulus of the cell wall, h is the thickness of the cell wall, R is the radius of the cell, l is the length of the cell and μ is the viscosity matrix (as described in [16]).

1.4 Micro-Dynamics of Transport and Fluid Flow in Pollen Tubes

1.4.1 Molecular Transport of Solutes

In Section 1.2 we discussed how free Ca^{2+} are thought to encourage myosin-11 to release transport vesicles as well as promote the exocytosis of these vesicles. To grasp how ions such as Ca^{2+} might effect growth we need to develop our understanding of how substrates are transported through the pollen tube. The equation which governs molecular transport is the continuity equation which is a direct result of the divergence theorem and states that

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{j} = R \quad (3.1)$$

where C is the concentration of a substance, R describes the role of sources and sinks (adding or removing the substance directly from the system) and \mathbf{j} is the flux vector representing the transport of the substance through a given point. The flux vector can be separated into the diffusive flux (transport via diffusion) and the advective flux (the transport of a substance by the bulk motion of a fluid) to get the advection-diffusion equation:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \left(\underbrace{-D\nabla C}_{\text{Diffusive flux}} \quad \underbrace{+\mathbf{v}C}_{\text{Advective flux}} \right) + R \quad (3.2)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient and \mathbf{v} is the velocity field of the fluid the substance is moving in.

In the context of Ca^{2+} transport in the tip of a pollen tube, we can make a number of simplifications to (3.2). The first is that R can only be non zero if Ca^{2+} are either reactants or products of a chemical reaction. Since we are aware that Ca^{2+} only form the cross-links in the cell wall and that bigger organelles are largely absent from the tip [9], we can assume that the role of sinks and sources is negligible within the tip. Pierson makes the observation that molecular transport in the tip is primarily governed by diffusion [44]. This means that the advection term is negligible in comparison to the diffusion term (again only in the tip). Furthermore, if we assume that the medium through which calcium is transported is isotropic, that is, its properties (like density, composition and structure) are uniform throughout, then we can say that the diffusion coefficient is constant. Finally, we can consider the steady state solution, that is, the case when the distribution of Ca^{2+} is not time dependent. All of these considerations put together mean that the general advection-diffusion system given in (3.2) simplifies to the steady-state isotropic diffusion equation:

$$\nabla^2 C = 0. \quad (3.3)$$

While these assumptions may be appropriate for the tip, they may not be for other areas of the pollen tube. For example, in [30], Kroeger considers the diffusion of Ca^{2+} down the shank of the pollen tube. While he still considers the steady state solution, the medium to be isotropic, the effect of advection to be negligible and the diffusion coefficient to be constant; he recognises that the endoplasmic reticulum, mitochondria, and vacuole are all binding sites for Ca^{2+} and therefore act as sinks. He made the additional assumption that these binding sites are distributed uniformly through the shank so that the rate of binding is directly proportional to the concentration of Ca^{2+} at that site, $R = -a^2C$ where a is a constant. Since Kroeger was primarily concerned with calcium distributions down the shank, he assumed that C was a function of the axial distance only, x say, and that the concentration at the apical fringe was a constant, C_0 say. This resulted in the following simplification of the general advection-diffusion system given in (3.2) (its schematic can be seen in Figure 5):

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^2 C - a^2 C &= 0 \quad \text{on } \Omega, \\ C &= C_0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_D, \\ C &< \infty \quad \text{on } \Omega, \end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

where $\Omega = \{x > 0\}$ and $\partial\Omega_D = \{x = 0\}$,
 C varies in the x direction only.

(3.4) then gave the following unique solution:

$$C = C_0 e^{-ax}. \tag{3.5}$$

Kroeger was able to approximate the value of a as being $50\mu\text{m}^{-1}$ with the use of additional information [30].

This approximation of an exponential decay of Ca^{2+} concentration down the shank of the pollen tube is a very simple one that can help explain some of the key features of pollen tube growth. For example, this model for Ca^{2+} distribution suggests a steep drop-off in concentration from the apical fringe. If we remind ourselves of what effect calcium has, it promotes the release of vesicles from the actin as well as their fusion to the cell membrane. Therefore, a steep drop off of calcium concentration down the shank from the apical fringe would

Figure 5: Schematic of the calcium diffusion system down the shank of the pollen tube that Kroeger formulated in [30] and is represented in system 3.4.

suggest that the vesicles (which deliver new cell wall material) are retained on the actin and any free floating vesicles that might exist will not fuse with the cell membrane. This means that despite the simplicity of Kroeger’s model, it is capable of explaining how growth is centred at the tip of the pollen tube and how the radius of the shank remains constant. However, we should note that the assumption of negligible advection in the shank of the tube is questionable. The movement of vesicles along the actin will create a flow of their own in the shank [52]. While a very steep exponential decrease in concentration down the axial length (as was the case with calcium) is unlikely to be changed significantly by even moderate fluid flow, the same might not be true for other solutes in the cytoplasm. This means that while Kroeger’s approach of dropping the advection term may have been reasonable for calcium, we should be sceptical about doing the same for other molecular transport systems. Developing meaningful models for the transportation of other solutes will then require incorporating some degree of knowledge of fluid flow in the shank, a completely non-trivial task that requires further analysis.

1.4.2 Fluid Flow in the Shank

The fluid that makes up the cytoplasm in the cell isn’t stationary, it responds to the movement of membrane bound organelles within the cell and flows freely [54]. The fluid flow in the cell will then play a significant role in how substances necessary for growth are transported. The equations used to describe fluid flow are called the Navier-Stokes equations and are given by:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \underbrace{\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}}_{\text{convection}} = \underbrace{-\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p}_{\text{pressure gradient}} + \underbrace{\nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}}_{\text{viscous forces}} + \underbrace{\mathbf{f}}_{\text{external forcing}} \quad (4.1)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the velocity vector field, p is the pressure field, ρ is the density, ν is the kinematic viscosity (a measure of a fluid’s resistance to flow), t is time and \mathbf{f} is the external forces per unit mass. There are many ways in which assumptions can be introduced to simplify this equation. The most intuitive simplification comes from considering the case where the velocity vector field is steady (has no time dependency). The second is to assume the body is in a closed system and that no external forces act on it. The least straight forward assumption comes from the actual property of the fluid. The Reynold’s number of a fluid is given by $Re = \frac{uL}{\nu}$ (where L is the characteristic length) and characterises the nature of the fluid’s flow. Fluids that have a low Reynold’s number have dominant viscous forces leading to negligible convection and a smooth and orderly flow. If each of the three assumptions are made then we recover a Stokes flow:

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p = \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}. \quad (4.2)$$

Deriving analytical solutions to the Navier-Stokes equations is a notoriously difficult task even when a number of assumptions and simplifications have been

made. An alternative approach that can lead to practical applications is that of a numerical approximation. In [52], Tyrell uses the method of regularised Stokeslets rings to model cytoplasmic streaming rates in the shank of the pollen tube. This mathematical technique involves expressing the flow induced by a point force (Stokeslet) acting on the fluid as a function of the force applied and the distance from the point of application. By superimposing the contribution from each Stokeslet, the total velocity field around the object can be calculated. In the context of fluid flow in the shank of a pollen tube, Tyrell considered the myosin transporting vesicles along the actin bundles to be the main driving force for cytoplasmic streaming. He then acknowledges that actin bundles can be spatially separated into the periphery and the centre of the tube.

Figure 6: (a) Schematic of the arrangement of Stokeslets and desired regions in the shank of the pollen tube that Tyrell used to model fluid flow. (b) An example of the fluid flow in a pollen tube that was computed using (4.3). Reproduced from [52].

This meant that he was able to form Stokeslet rings by combining the point forces at the periphery of the tube- the point forces at the centre remained point Stokeslets (see Figure 6(a)). The final thing Tyrell did was regularise the Stokeslets. This involves introducing a regularisation (smoothing) parameter which effectively spreads out the point force over a small region, eliminating

the singularity. Here, the regions in which the actin bundles were observed to be most concentrated were identified as the desired regions over which the Stokeslets were to be smoothed over.

The numerical system Tyrell derived for the non-azimuthal case was given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_r(\mathbf{x}) \\ u_z(\mathbf{x}) \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{8\pi\nu} \sum_{n=1}^N \begin{bmatrix} R_{rr}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_n) & R_{rz}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_n) \\ R_{zr}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_n) & R_{zz}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_n) \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} g_r(\mathbf{x}_n) \\ g_z(\mathbf{x}_n) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4.3)$$

Here, $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x})$ is the velocity at an arbitrary point \mathbf{x} , N is the number of Stokeslets, ε is the smoothing parameter and $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_n)$ is the force at Stokeslet n . The terms of the form $R_{ij}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_n)$ are known as the 'ringlet kernels' and represent how much influence the j -th component of the n -th regularised Stokeslet has on i -th component of the fluid velocity at point \mathbf{x} . The only thing that is unknown up to this point are the forces associated with the Stokeslets, $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_n)$. These can be determined by inverting (4.3) to make $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_n)$ the subject and then setting $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_n$. Note that this requires knowledge about $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_n)$, the velocity at each of the Stokeslets. An example of a fluid flow that (4.3) produces is given in Figure 6(b).

While it is apparent that input parameters like the fluid velocities at the Stokeslets, $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_n)$, will impact the resulting fluid flow, Tyrell highlights the substantial sensitivity the velocity field has to the regularisation parameter, ε [52]. This suggests that the actin configuration within the shank of the pollen tube plays an important role in how vesicles are transported and the resulting fluid flow. A core strength of this model is then that it can compare the fluid flows that would result from the different actin arrangements (by changing ε). In addition, Tyrell's model also encapsulates the role the central actin bundle has in generating flow. While the movement of vesicles in the centre has been observed, the role they play in generating fluid flow has only been hypothesised and not yet demonstrated so explicitly [6].

Although Tyrell recognises vesicles in pollen tubes as a generator of flow, he does not account for other sub-cellular structures that may restrict cytoplasmic streaming. Another limitation of his model is that the analysis of the effects of its input parameters is non-trivial in comparison to that of its analytic counterparts. However, it may be possible to mitigate against this limitation by using the model alongside some of the simpler analytical models. If the analytic models are used to develop an understanding of the effects of the parameters, Tyrell's more comprehensive model could then be used to verify these interpretations.

1.4.3 Effect of Electromagnetic Fields on Charged Particles

A key factor affecting the growth dynamics in pollen tubes is the distribution of ions within the cell, especially that of Ca^{2+} [47]. The movement of charged particles can be influenced by external factors, one such factor is the presence

of electromagnetic fields. The mechanism through which electromagnetic fields effect charged particles is governed by the Lorentz force which is given by

$$\mathbf{F} = q(\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}). \quad (5.1)$$

Here, \mathbf{F} is the force on the charged particle (due to the electromagnetic field), q is the charge of the particle, \mathbf{E} represents the electric field, \mathbf{v} is the velocity of the charged particle and \mathbf{B} represents the magnetic field. To compare the effects of the 2 fields on charged particles, we will consider each of them in isolation. Since we are mostly concerned with the movement of Ca^{2+} , we will assume from hereon out that q is positive.

Figure 7: (a) The parabolic trajectory a charged particle, q , follows in an electric field, \mathbf{E} . (b) The helical trajectory a charged particle, q , with velocity \mathbf{v} follows in a magnetic field \mathbf{B} .

First, for a purely electric field ($\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{0}$), (5.1) reduces down to $\mathbf{F} = q\mathbf{E}$. This indicates that the force on the charged particle is in the same direction of the electric field. Therefore, the charged particle is accelerated in the direction of the electric field and will follow a parabolic trajectory whose direction approaches that of the electric field (see Figure 7(a)). One thing to note is that the direction of motion that the particle approaches is strictly parallel to the electric field (not antiparallel). In addition, the rate of approach is proportional to the charge of the particle and the strength of the magnetic field.

The case for a purely magnetic field ($\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{0}$) is a little more complicated. Firstly, we have the reduction of (5.1) to $\mathbf{F} = q(\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B})$. The direction of the force is then in the direction that is mutually orthogonal to both \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{B} . This results

in a helical trajectory (see Figure 7(b)). To understand the coiling trajectory we will split \mathbf{v} into components that are parallel (or antiparallel) to \mathbf{B} , $\mathbf{v}_{\text{parallel}}$ say, and perpendicular to \mathbf{B} , $\mathbf{v}_{\text{perpendicular}}$ say, so that $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}_{\text{parallel}} + \mathbf{v}_{\text{perpendicular}}$. Then,

$$\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} = (\mathbf{v}_{\text{parallel}} \times \mathbf{B}) + (\mathbf{v}_{\text{perpendicular}} \times \mathbf{B}) = \mathbf{v}_{\text{perpendicular}} \times \mathbf{B}, \quad (5.3)$$

so $|\mathbf{F}| = q|\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}| = qvB$ where $v = |\mathbf{v}_{\text{perpendicular}}|$ and $B = |\mathbf{B}|$. Since the force never acts in the same direction as $\mathbf{v}_{\text{parallel}}$ (and therefore doesn't change it), we can equate the force exerted by the magnetic field on the charged particle to the centripetal force and get

$$\frac{mv^2}{r} = Bqv. \quad (5.4)$$

Rearranging for r gives $r = \frac{mv}{Bq}$ where r is the radius of the helix. Unlike an electric field, the acceleration caused by the magnetic field doesn't cause a change in speed of the charged particle. If we have that $|\mathbf{v}_{\text{parallel}}| \gg v$ and $1 \gg r$ (i.e. $Bq \gg mv$) then the trajectories of the charged particles are almost straight lines aligned with the direction of \mathbf{B} . Note that we haven't excluded the possibility that $\mathbf{v}_{\text{parallel}}$ is antiparallel to \mathbf{B} . This means that the alignment of the trajectories of charged particle in a magnetic field can be split into being parallel or antiparallel (unlike electric fields where it is strictly parallel). We have shown that under certain conditions, the trajectories of charged particles can align themselves with both electric and magnetic fields.

1.5 Aims and Objectives

Ca^{2+} distribution, transport vesicle delivery and pressure have all been identified as key mechanisms through which pollen tubes regulate their growth. While different modelling approaches have been employed, the ways in which these signals are perceived and processed by pollen cells are still poorly understood.

We will use analytic techniques to model the fluid flow in the shank of the tube in terms of pressure and vesicle movement. This will build on our understanding of how these two drivers of cytoplasmic streaming work alongside one another to generate fluid velocities in the shank. In addition, we will establish whether pressure regulation is important in maintaining regular cytoplasmic streaming rates in pollen tubes.

The continuity equation along with the influence of calcium channels will be used to model the distribution of Ca^{2+} in the tip of the pollen tube. We will then study the effect of introducing an electric field on the distribution of Ca^{2+} to see if the oriented growth that pollen tubes undergo when placed in electromagnetic fields can be attributed to Ca^{2+} in the tip. The validity of our

modelling approach will also be asserted by comparing the outputs of the model with data from multiple experiments.

2 Mathematical Modelling of Pollen Tube Dynamics

2.1 Macro-Growth Models

2.1.1 Analysis of Observed Growth Rates

Jefferies hypothesised that Gompertz growth (equation (1.5)- see section 1.3.1) was a better model for the overall growth of a pollen tube than logistic growth (equation (1.3)- see section 1.3.1) due to the asymmetries in the observed growth rates [27]. To investigate the suitability of both models a little more closely we have plotted the average lengths of the pollen tubes against time along with both models (see Figure 8(a)).

Figure 8: (a) A plot of Jefferies’ data where the mean length at each time interval has been plotted (data reproduced from [27]). A logistic fit given by (1.3) as well as a Gompertz fit given by (1.5) have also been added (see section 1.3.1). The relevant parameters are approximated to be $K = 13.8mm$, $L_0 = 0.35mm$ and the initial gradient of the velocity vs. length graph was approximated as $1.6s^{-1}$. (b) A plot of the approximate growth speeds of pollen tubes derived from Jefferies’ data. A logistic and Gompertz fit was included via (1.1) and (1.4) respectively (see section 1.3.1). The values of the parameters are the same as in (a).

The terminal length, K , was taken to be the maximum of the averaged lengths the pollen tubes reached (13.8mm) and the initial length, L_0 , was found by propagating the data back to the y axis (0.35mm). The rate parameters were determined by approximating the initial gradient of the growth velocities against lengths (see Figure 8(b)). The plots in Figure 8(a) shows that, for the given parameters, the Gompertz model approximated the average growth of the pollen tubes better than the logistic growth model. In addition, Figure 8(b) highlights that logistic growth's inability to account for asymmetries in growth rates is quite significant when modelling pollen tube dynamics.

A more recent study, conducted by Fernandes and Larkin, also measured the growth of pollen tubes at regular time intervals [18]. Unlike Jefferies' data, the experiment ran by Fernandes and Larkin ran over a much shorter time span (a matter of minutes rather than days) which resulted in a smaller range of growth lengths (see Figure 10). In this experiment, pollen grains from fresh lillies (*Lilium longiflorum*) were harvested and placed into two 25x10mm petri dishes, each containing 9 grains. The grains were then germinated and placed horizontally in a vertical superconducting solenoid magnet (see Figure 9). The strength of the magnetic field varies spatially and was measured in terms of the relative gravitational field strength water would experience as a result of the diamagnetic force from the solenoid.

One of the petri dishes was placed at a $0g$ position (equivalent to $11.5T$) and the other at a $1g$ position (equivalent to $16.5T$). The development of the pollen tubes was monitored with the help of cameras placed above each petri dish. In addition, a control petri containing 8 freshly harvested pollen grains dish was placed horizontally on a bench in the absence of any magnetic field with a camera placed above it as well. The pollen tubes were grown in a temperature controlled environment. After 6 hours, the apparatus was disassembled. The footage from the cameras was then

Figure 9: The setup of the experiment Fernandez and Larkin ran to investigate the time lapsed growth of pollen tubes in different magnetic field strengths [18]. The data from this experiment can be seen in Figure 10.

analysed by first recording the position of the pollen grains and then (after a lag of 182 minutes) recording the heads of the pollen tubes at regular intervals. The recording of positions was done by playing the footage through a computer and clicking the cursor over the heads of the pollen tubes. The manual segmentation of growth allowed Fernandez and Larkin to compute a time lapse of their growth (see Figure 10). The results from this experiment suggest that pollen tubes initially grow with a constant rate. This contrasts the Logistic and Gompertz models proposed by Jefferies which suggest an initial exponential growth. However, this discrepancy could well be attributed to the significant difference in time spans between the two experiments. Comparing the cases for different magnetic field strengths, we see that the mean growth lengths are very similar between the cases (the error bars overlap for each time increment). However, an argument can be made for increased variability in stronger fields. More specifically, the variance of the tube lengths seems to grow more significantly for the pollen tubes in $1g$ in comparison the other 2 scenarios. More work could be done to determine at what time the variability in growth lengths for pollen tubes in magnetic fields becomes statistically different from those not in magnetic fields. It is not entirely clear why a stronger magnetic field may lead to an increased variability in tube lengths and additional analysis of how growth mechanisms respond to electromagnetic fields is required to explain such a phenomena.

Figure 10: (a) Pollen tube lengths with respect to time without a magnetic field. (b) Pollen tube lengths with respect to time in a magnetic field of strength $11.5T$. (c) Pollen tube lengths with respect to time in the a magnetic field of strength $16.5T$. Note that the differenced lengths, $L - L_0$, have been plotted where L is the length at time t and L_0 is the length at 183 minutes. In addition, the initial (linear) growth rates for all the scenarios have also been stated. All data was retrieved from [18].

2.1.2 Analysis of Directed Growth

Figure 11: (a) Results of Sperber's study of oriented growth of pollen tubes in magnetic fields. Reproduced from [48]. (b) The setup of the experiment Fernandez and Larkin ran to investigate deflections of growth directions from a magnetic field [18]. The data from this experiment can be seen in Figure 12

A study run by Sperber concerned itself with the effect of magnets on the orientation of pollen tube growth [48]. His results are shown in Figure 11(a). We can see that it is possible that the tubes aligned themselves with the magnetic field in a parallel and antiparallel manner, similar to the one described by the charged particle trajectories. Sperber's results motivate the further investigation into the oriented growth of pollen tubes in magnetic fields to see whether any difference is due to chance and if not, how this difference can be explained.

Fernandez and Larkin ran another experiment, similar to the one described in section 2.1.1, but investigating how magnetic fields can affect the growth direction of pollen tubes. This time, a single petri dish containing 161 freshly harvested pollen grains (*Lilium longiflorum*) was placed vertically in the vertical superconducting solenoid such that the direction of the magnetic field was in the plane of growth (see Figure 11(b)). A control petri dish containing 110 pollen

grains was placed on a bench in the absence of a magnetic field. The pollen grains were germinated and left in a temperature controlled environment. After a period, the apparatus was disassembled and the mean direction of growth for each pollen tube was calculated by comparing the position of its head with the position of the grain. The results from this experiment are shown in Figure 12. Note that the study was primarily concerned with deviations in growth directions from the magnetic field; for this reason, deflections were in the range of -90° to 90° instead of 0° to 360° (where the magnetic field had direction 0°). Therefore, to get a better idea of the overall directions of growth, for every data point, θ say, in the raw data, $\theta + 180^\circ$ has also been added resulting in odd (antisymmetric) probability distribution functions. This was only done in Figure 12 as it eases visualisation of growth directions but isn't in any of following plots or statistical tests.

Figure 12: (a) Distribution of average growth directions of pollen tubes that haven't been magnetised. (b) Distribution of average growth directions of pollen tubes that have been Magnetised. All data retrieved from [18]

It would seem that Figure 12 suggests that Fernandez and Larkin's results are consistent with those of Sperber's. Namely, pollen tubes align themselves with magnetic fields in a parallel and antiparallel manor. We may also hypothesise that without the presence of a magnet, pollen tube growth is random and so the distribution of growth directions is uniform. When comparing distributions it is conventional to first run graphical diagnostics in the form of quantile-quantile (Q-Q) plots to find any systematic differences between the distributions. Q-Q plots for the control data vs a uniform distribution and for the magnetised data

vs a uniform distribution are given in Figure 13(a) and Figure 13(b) respectively. The Q-Q plot in Figure 13(a) could infer that the uniform distribution is a decent approximation for the control sample as any deviation away from the central line is similar along the length of the straight line and doesn't appear to be systematic. This isn't the case in Figure 13(b). Although the quantiles of the magnet sample closely match those of the uniform distribution for a large range of values, significant differences occur at the tails of the distributions. While this isn't usually considered important when analysing a Q-Q plot against a normal distribution, it is for a Q-Q plot against a uniform distribution. The substantial and systematic difference between the tails of the magnet sample and uniform distribution justify the claim that the magnet sample follows a modal distribution. Another thing we notice from the Q-Q plots in Figure 13(a) and Figure 13(b) is that there is a jump in the quantiles around 0° . Since this occurs in both the control sample and the magnet sample it is unlikely the jump is a result of the magnet or randomness. It is therefore reasonable to attribute this jump in quantiles to a systematic error in the experiment. Since the region around 0° is of strong significance to our conclusions we would recommend contacting Fernandez and Larkin for further details on how the results were collected.

Figure 13: Results from the experiment conducted by Larkin and Fernandez into how magnetic fields effect growth directions in pollen tubes [18]. Q-Q plots for the control sample vs the uniform distribution (a), the magnet sample vs the uniform distribution (b) and the magnet sample vs the control sample (c).

We may also want to compare the distributions of the magnet sample and the control sample directly. Figure 13(c) has a Q-Q plot for the quantiles of the magnet sample against the quantiles of the the control sample. It demonstrates some degree of similarity between the 2 sample distributions, however, as we may have suspected, there are differences in the tails of the 2 distributions. It should be noted that the sample size for the control data is 110 while the sample size for the magnet data is 161. Since these 2 values aren't the same, we weren't

able to construct a Q-Q plot directly. Instead, we randomly selected (without replacement) a subsample of 110 values from the magnet sample where each data point was equally likely to be chosen. This means that, while the Q-Q plot in Figure 13(c) is not unique, it is still representative of the 2 distributions and so is sufficient for the purposes of graphical diagnostics.

Q-Q plots are helpful in informing us about some of the underlying features of distributions but are subjective. There are many quantitative tests that can be used to compare distributions. For larger sample sizes (appropriate here) a common choice is Smirnov-Kolmogorov test whose test statistic is the maximum absolute difference between the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of the two datasets being compared. The CDFs of the control sample, the magnetic sample and the theoretical uniform distribution is given in Figure 14. We can use this test to see whether either the

Figure 14: CDFs of the control and magnet samples along with a theoretical uniform distribution from the oriented growth experiment ran by Fernandez and Larkin [18].

control or magnet samples can be distributed uniformly or whether the control and magnet samples have the same distribution. We will therefore conduct 3 hypothesis tests. It should be noted that the raw data was used here and not concatenated or diminished in any way as was done previously. The first hypothesis test is $H_0 : \text{Control sample} \sim U(-90, 90)$ vs. $H_1 : \text{Control sample} \approx U(-90, 90)$. The test statistic for the hypothesis test is 0.1229 which means the most the control sample and the uniform distribution ever differ by is 12.29% (full output as well as the code generating it is given in appendix). The p -value of this test is 0.0663. We can see that if a typical 5% significance level is chosen, H_0 will not be rejected which means that there is insufficient evidence to rule out the possibility that the control sample is uniformly distributed. It should be stated that the p -value (0.0663) is close to 0.05 so this conclusion is marginal so this test shouldn't be used in isolation.

The next hypothesis test is $H_0 : \text{Magnet sample} \sim U(-90, 90)$ vs. $H_1 : \text{Magnet sample} \approx U(-90, 90)$. The test statistic for the hypothesis test is 0.2913 which means the most the magnet sample and the uniform distribution ever differ by is 29.13%, over double that of control sample (full output as well as the code generating it is given in appendix). The p -value of this test is

2.0125×10^{-12} . We can see that, for any reasonable significance level, H_0 is rejected in favour of H_1 , so there is very strong evidence that the magnet sample is not taken from a uniform distribution.

The final hypothesis is H_0 : Magnet sample and control sample are from the same distribution vs. H_1 : Magnet sample and control sample aren't from the same distribution. The test statistic for the hypothesis test is 0.3477 which means the most the magnet sample and the uniform distribution ever differ by is 34.77% (full output as well as the code generating it is given in appendix). This even exceeds the test statistic between the magnet sample and the uniform distribution (29.13%). The p -value of this test is 1.6845×10^{-7} . We can see that, for any reasonable significance level, H_0 is rejected in favour of H_1 , so there is very strong evidence that introducing a magnet had an effect on the growth directions of the pollen tube. We have established the statistical significance of magnetic fields on growth directions in pollen tubes. Since our graphical diagnostics also suggested that they align themselves (in a parallel or antiparallel manner) with the direction of the magnetic field, it is now reasonable to try and model this phenomena as is done in section.

2.1.3 Growth as a Function of Vesicle Production

The exocytosis of transport vesicles to the cell membrane is essential to maintaining cell wall composition during growth. Consequently, it is intuitive to propose the rate at which vesicles are produced as a potential limiting factor for growth. Vesicles are produced by the golgi and rough endoplasmic reticulum, so we will use vesicle production as a measure of their combined activity.

In the formulation of our model we will assume that the radius of the pollen tube, R_0 say, is constant as well as the thickness, δ say, and density, ρ say, of the cell wall (see Figure 15(a)). These simplifications are often introduced as was done in the model formulated by Dyson and Jensen [16] (see section 1.3.2). If M is the rate at which the cell wall accumulates mass and m is the rate at which the golgi and rough endoplasmic reticulum produce mass, then, by the conservation of mass:

$$M(t) = \mu m(t) \tag{6.1}$$

where μ is the proportion of vesicles produced by the golgi and rough endoplasmic reticulum that reach the cell wall. We will assume that μ is constant throughout growth. Using the constant density assumption, we can update (6.1) to:

$$\rho \frac{dV}{dt} = \mu m(t) \tag{6.2}$$

Figure 15: (a) Schematic of how the exocytosis of vesicles to the cell membrane influences the cell wall. (b) Plot of (6.4) with $R_0 = 8.13\mu\text{ms}^{-1}$, $\rho = 10^3\text{kgm}^{-3}$, $\delta = 0.6\mu\text{m}$, $\mu = 0.17$ and varying values of m that correspond to typically observed growth rates.

where V is the volume of the cell wall. Because the radius of the cell and the thickness of the cell wall are assumed to be constant, any change in volume will have pipe-like structure. We can then say that $\Delta V = \Delta\pi l(R_0^2 - (R_0 - \delta)^2) = \Delta\pi l\delta(2R_0 - \delta)$ where l is the length of the pollen tube. Putting this into (6.2) then gives

$$\rho\pi\delta(2R_0 - \delta)\frac{dl}{dt} = \mu m(t), \quad (6.3)$$

which, on rearrangement and integration, becomes

$$l(t) = \frac{\mu}{\rho\pi\delta(2R_0 - \delta)} \int_0^t m(u) du + L_0 \quad (6.4)$$

where L_0 is the initial length of the tube. The values for radius of the cell as well as the density and thickness of the cell are well known and given by $8.13\mu\text{m}$, 10^3kgm^{-3} and $0.6\mu\text{m}$ respectively. The value of μ is less trivial, it is approximated to lie within $0.125 - 0.17$. We can now consider the limiting case where m is constant. This coincides with the case where the growth rate is constant. The experiment ran by Fernandez and Larkin found that the initial growth rate of pollen tubes was around $10\mu\text{m}(\text{min})^{-1} \approx 0.17\mu\text{ms}^{-1}$ (see section). We can then rearrange (6.3) to see that the necessary value of m to observe growth rates of $0.17\mu\text{ms}^{-1}$ is in the region of $3 \times 10^{-15}\text{kggs}^{-1}$. We can then plot (6.4) for a range of typically observed growth rates and their respective values of m (see Figure 15(b)). While there are numerous simplifications that this model employs, it does give us an idea of the magnitude of the vesicle production by the golgi and rough endoplasmic reticulum. To gain a better understanding of how vesicles and solvents produced in sub-cellular organelles relate to cell growth we need to know how they are transported up the shank of the pollen tube.

2.2 Micro-Dynamics

2.2.1 Fluid Flow in the Shank

Table 1: Parameter values for the fluid flow in the shank

Parameter	Units	Value (range)	Reference
Radius (<i>Lilium longiflorum</i>), r_0	μm	8.13	[36]
Velocity of vesicles at peripheral actin, u^+	μms^{-1}	0.5	[6]
Velocity of vesicles at central actin, $-u^-$	μms^{-1}	-0.5	[6]
Dynamic viscosity (water), μ	$\text{kgm}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$	10^{-3}	[36]
Reynold's number (<i>Lilium longiflorum</i>), Re	-	2.9×10^{-6}	[36]

Figure 16: (a) Representation of the shank of the pollen tube in cylindrical polar coordinates. (b) The fluid flow within the shank of the pollen tube with transportation of fluid towards the apical region happening at the exterior and removal of fluid from the apex happening at the interior.

The shank of the pollen tube is the transport system used by vesicles and solutes to move to and from the apical region. For angiosperms, substances are transported to the tip at the periphery of the shank and are returned via the centre (see Figure 16(b)). The radius of the pollen tube has been observed to be constant making the shank of the tube have a cylindrical structure; we will therefore use cylindrical polar coordinates to model the fluid flow (see Figure 16(a)). We will

assume that the velocity near the cell wall, u^+ say, and the velocity the cell near the centre, u^- say, are known (see Figure 16(b)). These will form the boundary conditions for our model. Note that moving boundary conditions can sometimes be interpreted as sliding wall problems. However, we know that the cell walls in the shank of the tube are stationary. In the context of our model, the sliding walls will be the vesicles moving along the actin filaments. Therefore, u^+ and u^- represent the velocities of the vesicles moving along the peripheral and central actin bundles respectively. This is similar to the approach used by Tyrell to model fluid flow in the shank (see section 1.4.2). In the shank of the tube, cytoplasmic streaming has been observed to occur almost entirely length ways and for lengths greater than approximately five times the radius, cytoplasmic streaming is the same along the length of the tube [43] (independent of z). If we also assume the flow is axisymmetric then the velocity of the fluid in the shank can be given by $\mathbf{u} = [0, 0, u_z(r)]^T$. We will consider the steady state system when there are no external forces acting on the body. Together with the approximation of Reynolds number in the shank to be 2.9×10^{-6} , it is also reasonable to assume the Navier-Stokes equations simplify to a Stokes flow in the shank of the tube. This leaves us with the following problem formulation:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla p &= \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}, \\ u_z(r = r_0) &= u^+, \\ u_z(r = \delta) &= -u^-, \end{aligned} \tag{7.1}$$

where μ is the dynamic viscosity, and r_0 and δ are the locations of the vesicles on the central and periphery actin bundles (whose velocities are known) respectively. Given that $\mathbf{u} = [0, 0, u_z(r)]^T$, we must have $\nabla^2 \mathbf{u} = \nabla^2 u_z(r)$. It therefore follows that $\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} = \frac{\partial p}{\partial \theta} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial p}{\partial z}$ is constant (as it be a function of r only). Since $\frac{\partial p}{\partial z}$ is constant, we can interpret $\frac{\partial p}{\partial z}$ as the pressure gradient up the length of the pollen tube. To ease notation, from hereon out, $u_z(r) = u$. Then, expanding the Laplacian operator in cylindrical polar coordinates within the stokes flow equation gives us:

$$\frac{\mu}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{du}{dr} \right) = \frac{dp}{dz}. \tag{7.2}$$

Once again we will non-dimensionalise the problem by introducing new variables, $r = r' r_0$ and $u = u' u^+$. We will assume $r_0 \approx$ radius of the pollen tube, so the interpretation of r' is then the ratio between the radius of the pollen tube and the current radial position. Similarly, u' can be interpreted as the ratio between the fluid velocity at the exterior of the pollen tube and the current fluid velocity. Implementing this change in variable within (7.2) and rearranging leads to

$$\frac{d}{dr'} \left(r' \frac{du'}{dr'} \right) = \frac{r_0^2}{\mu u^+} \frac{dp}{dz} r' = 4A r' \tag{7.3}$$

where $A = 4 \frac{r_0^2}{\mu u^+} \frac{dp}{dz}$ can be interpreted as a dimensionless constant (since $\frac{dp}{dz}$ is a constant). The factor of 4 will ease notation later. Upon integrating we see

that

$$\int \frac{d}{dr'} \left(r' \frac{du'}{dr'} \right) dr' = \int 4Ar' dr',$$

$$r' \frac{du'}{dr'} = 2A(r')^2 + B \quad (7.4)$$

where B is a dimensionless constant. Again, we can rearrange and integrate, leaving us with

$$\int \frac{du'}{dr'} dr' = \int 2A'r' + \frac{B}{r'} dr',$$

$$u' = A(r')^2 + B \log(r') + C \quad (7.5)$$

where C is a dimensionless constant. Although the log function will diverge as r' approaches 0 (which would lead to us setting B to 0), we note that our boundary conditions mean that our solution is only required to hold for $0 < \frac{\delta}{r_0} \leq r' \leq r_0$. We can therefore conclude that $\log(r')$ will remain finite within our system which means that B is not necessarily 0 and so we keep it as a currently unknown constant. We now have 3 unknown constants (A , B and C) and 2 boundary equations. We will use the boundary conditions to write (7.5) in terms of 1 unknown constant. Before we implement them, we will introduce two new variables to further ease notation, namely $\alpha = \frac{\delta}{r_0}$ and $\beta = \frac{-u^-}{u^+}$. Therefore, α and β represent the choices where data has been collected. We can then write the boundary conditions in terms of the non-dimensional variables: $u'(r' = 1) = 1$ and $u'(r' = \alpha) = \beta$. This leads to the the following simultaneous equation:

$$1 = A + C, \quad (7.7)$$

$$\beta = A\alpha^2 + B \log(\alpha) + C.$$

This system can be solved to get

$$C = 1 - A \quad \text{and} \quad B = \frac{\beta + A(1 - \alpha^2) - 1}{\log(\alpha)}. \quad (7.8)$$

The constants in (7.8) can then be plugged into (7.5) which leads to:

$$u' = A(r')^2 + \left[\frac{\beta + A(1 - \alpha^2) - 1}{\log(\alpha)} \right] \log(r') + 1 - A. \quad (7.9)$$

If we want to redimensionalise this solution we can do so and get

$$u = u^+ \left\{ A \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^2 + \left[\frac{\beta + A(1 - \alpha^2) - 1}{\log(\alpha)} \right] \log \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right) + 1 - A \right\}. \quad (7.10)$$

There are now 3 parameters that define the velocity field: A , α and β . The boundary conditions supply us with all the information needed to compute α and β but A remains an unknown constant. One way of approximating A would be to measure the pressure at different points in the tube and then compute the

pressure gradient. Unfortunately, such data is very hard to come by. However, we can propose an alternative approach to estimating A by using typical growth speeds. Since α and β are known, if A is also known, we will have a unique velocity profile which will coincide with a unique volumetric flow rate. We can then consider an 'average' flow velocity which will be approximated by the growth speed (assuming the entry and exit of fluid into the cell is negligible as is done in [55]).

The volumetric flow rate, Q say, is given by $Q = \int \int_{\mathcal{A}} u d\mathcal{A}$ where \mathcal{A} is an area element from the cross section of the pollen tube (a circle of radius r_0). In cylindrical polar coordinates this is

$$Q = \int_{r=\delta}^{r=r_0} \int_{\theta=0}^{\theta=2\pi} ur d\theta dr. \quad (7.11)$$

By assumption, u does not depend on θ so we can integrate to get

$$Q = 2\pi \int_{r=\delta}^{r=r_0} ur dr, \quad (7.12)$$

which, after rearranging leads to

$$\frac{Q}{2\pi} = \int_{r=\delta}^{r=r_0} ur dr. \quad (7.13)$$

If we now introduce the idea of an 'average' flow velocity, we must have that $Q = \bar{u}\pi r_0^2$ where \bar{u} is the average flow rate (approximated by the known growth rate). Substituting $Q = \bar{u}\pi r_0^2$ and the expression for u' found in in (7.10) into (7.13) leaves us with

$$\frac{\bar{u}r_0^2}{2} = \int_{r=\delta}^{r=r_0} u + \left\{ A \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^2 + \left[\frac{\beta + A(1 - \alpha^2) - 1}{\log(\alpha)} \right] \log \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right) + 1 - A \right\} r dr. \quad (7.14)$$

Since the integrand is linear in A , (7.14) can be integrated and rearranged to for A . As \bar{u} is known, (7.14) represents the 3rd condition to the problem meaning a unique A can be computed from it.

Figure 17: (a) Cytoplasmic streaming data for *Nitella Fexilis* (algae) reproduced from [41]. (b) Plots of the velocity field defined by equation 7.10 with $\delta = 1\mu m$, $-u^- = 1\mu m/s$, $r_0 = 120\mu m$, $u^+ = 66\mu m/s$, $\beta = 0.0152$, $\alpha = 0.0083$ and varying values of A (which correspond to typically observed growth speeds) alongside the Mustarich and Ware data.

In order to assert the validity of our assumptions, it would be helpful to compare the output of this model with some known data. Namely, for a set of boundary conditions and a growth speed, does our resultant model fit interpolant data well. Unfortunately, the relevant cytoplasmic streaming data for pollen tubes is very hard find. As an alternative we can use the cytoplasmic streaming data from organisms that grow in a similar way. Here, we have selected the cytoplasmic streaming data for *Nitella Fexilis* (algae) from Mustarich and Ware [41] (see Figure 17(a)). Although there are some differences in the growth mechanisms between algae and pollen tubes, the fundamental assumptions of the relevant dynamics such as a cylindrical structure and cytoplasmic streaming that acts almost entirely axially still hold [36]. From this data we will use the outer data points as the boundary conditions, namely $(\delta, -u^-) = (1, 1)$ and $(r_0, u^+) = (120, 66)$ (which gives $\alpha = 0.0083$ and $\beta = 0.0152$). Mustarich and Ware also stated that they observed the growth rate to lie between $25\text{-}55 \mu m/s$ [41]. Using this information and solving for A in (7.14) means that, for our boundary conditions, we can expect the value of A to lie between $0.25\text{-}1$. The plot of the velocity field given in (7.10) can be seen in Figure 17(b) for values of A within 0.25 and 1 alongside the cytoplasmic streaming data. We can see that almost all of the interpolant data lies comfortably within this band and that some values of A correspond very closely to almost all of the observed data. This suggests that our approach is likely adequate in producing representative models.

We are now ready to use our model to approximate the velocity field in the

shank of the pollen tube. Vesicles at the periphery of the cell have been observed to move with velocities up to $0.5\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ whereas vesicles in the centre of the tube move at $-0.5\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ [6]. Tyrell used these values in his model formulation (see section 1.4.2) as well as a growth speed of $0.1\mu\text{m}\text{s}^{-1}$ [52]. It would be useful to compare our model output to his (see Figure 18(b)) so we will use input parameters: $\delta = 0.1\mu\text{m}$, $-u^- = -0.5\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$, $r_0 = 8.13\mu\text{m}$, $u^+ = 0.5\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ (producing $\beta = -1$ and $\alpha = 0.083$), and $\bar{u} = 0.1\mu\text{m}\text{s}^{-1}$. Computing (7.14) and solving for A (using the stated parameters) gives $A = 1.48$. We can then find the velocity field given by 7.10 which has been plotted in Figure 18(a).

Figure 18: (a) Plots of the velocity field defined by (7.10) with $\delta = 0.01\mu\text{m}$, $-u^- = -0.5\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$, $r_0 = 8.13\mu\text{m}$, $u^+ = 0.5\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$, $\beta = 0.0152$, $\alpha = 0.0083$ and $\bar{u} = 0.1\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ (which produces $A = 1.48$ from (7.14)). (b) Output of the Tyrell's Stokeslets rings model with the same boundary conditions as used in (a) (reproduced from [52]).

Although there are slight differences in the velocity fields between the models, we can see that our model captures all of the main features of the Stokeslets rings model within the shank of the tube. The differences between the two is

likely due to the Stokeslets rings model incorporating cytoplasmic streaming in the tip as well as considering more elaborate configurations of actin bundles. However, the model we have created is far simpler and still has a relatively high degree of correspondence to the more complicated Stokeslets model which means the interpretations of our model could be useful. Before we investigate the effect each parameter has on the model, it is important to remember that the velocity profile is in cylindrical polar coordinates and so is in 3D. Figure 19 is a plot of the velocity profile given in (7.10) with the same input parameters as those used in Figure 18(a).

In order to interpret our model we need to investigate how each of our parameters, α , β and A , affect the velocity profile given in (7.10). The easiest way to do this is by plotting (7.10) for varying values of our parameters (see Figure 20). The baseline values of the parameters are $\alpha = 0.0123$, $\beta = -1$ and $A = 0.22$. Each parameter was then varied while keeping the other two constant. The parameter $\alpha = \frac{\delta}{r_0}$ potentially has the most straightforward interpretation: it sets the domain over which the velocity profile is valid (see Figure 20(a)). Increasing α shortens the domain but without a significant change to the velocity profile's shape. The parameter $\beta = \frac{-u^-}{u^+}$ represents the ratio at which the two 'walls' are sliding (see Figure 20(b)). We see that the larger β becomes (i.e. the more similar the sliding 'walls' are), the more the velocity profile is smoothed out. Smaller β lead to singularities at the centre. Note that, we are primarily concerned with the cytoplasmic streaming in angiosperms, pollen tubes where vesicles move towards the apex at the periphery and back via the centre. It therefore only makes sense to consider the cases where $\beta \leq 1$.

Figure 19: Plots of the velocity field defined by (7.10) with $\delta = 0.01\mu\text{m}$, $-u^- = -0.5\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$, $r_0 = 8.13\mu\text{m}$, $u^+ = 0.5\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$, $\beta = 0.0152$, $\alpha = 0.0083$ and $\bar{u} = 0.1\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ (which produces $A = 1.48$ from (7.14)).

The parameter $A \propto \frac{dp}{dz}$, the pressure gradient, represents the forcing agent on the fluid flow (see Figure 20(c)). Note that, if the pressure is higher nearer the pollen grain and lower nearer the apex, A will be negative. Intuitively, this pressure difference will result in fluid being forced up the shank of the pollen tube (towards the apex). Conversely, if the pressure is lower nearer the pollen grain and higher nearer the apex, A will be positive. The pressure difference will then suppress fluid moving up the the shank of the pollen tube (towards the apex). These features can be seen in Figure 20(c) where negative values of A result in more fluid moving towards the apex and vice versa. Additionally, we can see that as $|A|$ increases, the velocity profile becomes less regular (causing singularities at the centre).

As mentioned in section 1.3.2, pollen tubes are able to regulate their pressure (through osmosis) much faster than they are able to make structural changes like actin reconfiguration or vesicle production [59]. It therefore stands to reason that flow regulation in the shank is primarily controlled through pressure. This means that the pressure gradient, A , plays a greater role in maintaining a smooth velocity profile than the sliding 'walls', β . We would therefore expect β to be relatively constant in comparison to A .

Figure 20: Plots of the velocity profile given in (7.10). The baseline values of the parameters are $\alpha = 0.0123$, $\beta = -1$ and $A = 0.22$. α , β and A are then varied in turn to create the plots seen in (a), (b) and (c) respectively.

2.2.2 Calcium Ion Distribution in the Tip

Table 2: Parameter values for the Ca^{2+} in the tip

Parameter	Units	Value (range)	Reference
Diffusion coefficient, D	$m^2 s^{-1}$	10^{-9}	[36]
Ca^{2+} concentration at apical fringe, C_0	nM	500	[24]

Closed System Model The concentration of Ca^{2+} plays a key role in how vesicles are absorbed by the cell wall and is therefore a major underlying factor effecting growth. Ca^{2+} are transported into the tip by calcium channels which are most active at the very tip of the apical region and decrease symmetrically down the sides of the cell [23] (see Figure 21(b)). We will therefore propose that $\frac{\partial C}{\partial r} \propto \cos \theta$ on the surface of the tip so that the forcing agents taking Ca^{2+} across the cell boundary are most prominent at the very apex and negligible at the apical fringe.

Figure 21: (a) A schematic of the hemispherical tip of the pollen tube with its Neumann and Dirichlet boundaries labelled. (b) An illustration of the calcium channel activity on the surface of the tip as well as the hypothesised constant concentration of Ca^{2+} on the apical fringe.

Since pollen tubes have been observed to have constant radius, we could guess that Ca^{2+} diffuse evenly down the shank of the pollen tube and so the concentration of Ca^{2+} is constant at the apical fringe. In addition, transport

vesicles have been observed to move primarily through diffusion in the tube [44]. This suggests that the effects of cytoplasmic streaming (and therefore advection) on molecular transport in the tip is negligible in comparison to diffusion. Furthermore, larger organelles are largely absent in the tip of a pollen tube [9]. Not only does this mean it is reasonable to assume that the medium through which Ca^{2+} moves is isotropic but also that there are no sources or sinks in the tip (as there are no binding sites for the Ca^{2+}). If we assume the distribution of Ca^{2+} doesn't change over time, we can then say that molecular transport in the tip is governed by the steady state isotropic diffusion equation.

The hemispherical shape of the tip means that spherical polar coordinates is a reasonable choice to model the calcium concentration (see Figure 21(a)). The problem can then be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^2 C &= 0 & \text{on } \Omega, \\ C &= C_0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega_D, \\ D \frac{\partial C}{\partial r} &= q_0 \cos \theta & \text{on } \partial\Omega_N, \\ 0 \leq C &< \infty & \text{on } \Omega, \end{aligned} \tag{8.1}$$

$$\text{where } \partial\Omega_D = \{(r, \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r \leq r_0, \theta = \frac{\pi}{2}\},$$

$$\partial\Omega_N = \{(r, \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r \leq r_0, 0 \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}\},$$

$$\text{and } \Omega = \text{int}\{\partial\Omega_D \cup \partial\Omega_N\}.$$

Here, r_0 is the radius of the pollen tube, C_0 is the baseline concentration of Ca^{2+} on the apical fringe, D is the diffusion coefficient and q_0 is the strength of the calcium channel relative to the diffusion coefficient. The problem formulation is illustrated in Figure 21. If we assume that the concentration is symmetrical about the centreline (i.e. independent of ϕ), expanding the Laplacian in spherical coordinates gives

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial C}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta} \right) = 0. \tag{8.2}$$

We can non-dimensionalise the problem by introducing C' and r' where $C = C_0(C' + 1)$ and $r = r_0 r'$. C' is then ratio between a surplus concentration and the concentration at the apical fringe. Similarly; r' is the ratio between the radius at a given point and the radius of the boundary. Substituting these

variables into (8.1) gives the non-dimensional problem:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{r'^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r'} \left(r'^2 \frac{\partial C'}{\partial r'} \right) + \frac{1}{r'^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial C'}{\partial \theta} \right) &= 0 \quad \text{on } \Omega, \\
C' &= 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_D, \\
\frac{\partial C'}{\partial r'} &= \mu \cos \theta \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_N, \\
-1 \leq C' < \infty &\quad \text{on } \Omega,
\end{aligned} \tag{8.3}$$

where $\partial\Omega_D = \{(r', \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r' \leq 1, \theta = \frac{\pi}{2}\}$,
 $\partial\Omega_N = \{(r', \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r' \leq 1, 0 \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}\}$,
and $\Omega = \text{int}\{\partial\Omega_D \cup \partial\Omega_N\}$.

Here, $\mu = \frac{q_0 r_0}{C_0 D}$ is a constant. We will propose an Ansatz with separated variables:

$$C'(r', \theta) = R(r')\Theta(\theta). \tag{8.4}$$

Implementing (8.4) into the dynamics equation in (8.3) gives:

$$\frac{\Theta}{r'^2} \frac{d}{dr'} \left(r'^2 \frac{dR}{dr'} \right) + \frac{R}{r'^2 \sin \theta} \frac{d}{d\theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{d\Theta}{d\theta} \right) = 0. \tag{8.5}$$

Upon expanding and rearranging,

$$\frac{1}{R} \left(2r' \frac{dR}{dr'} + r'^2 \frac{d^2 R}{dr'^2} \right) = \frac{-1}{\Theta \sin \theta} \left(\cos \theta \frac{d\Theta}{d\theta} + \sin \theta \frac{d^2 \Theta}{d\theta^2} \right). \tag{8.6}$$

We can see that the left hand side (LHS) of (8.6) is a function of r' only and the right hand side (RHS) is a function of θ only. Consequently, both sides must be equal to a constant, λ say. If we consider the RHS of (8.6), we then get

$$\sin \theta \frac{d^2 \Theta}{d\theta^2} + \cos \theta \frac{d\Theta}{d\theta} + \lambda \sin \theta \Theta = 0. \tag{8.7}$$

The objective is now to determine for which values of λ a solution to (8.7) exists and what form the corresponding function Θ takes. Although it is not immediately clear, (8.7) actually has the form of a Legendre equation (a well studied equation). We can demonstrate this relation explicitly by introducing the variables $x = \cos \theta$ and $P(x) = \Theta(\theta)$. Rewriting (8.7) in terms of P and then rearranging gives

$$\frac{d^2 P}{dx^2} + \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{dP}{dx} + \lambda P = 0 \tag{8.8}$$

where we have assumed that $\sin \theta \neq 0$ which corresponds to $|x| < 1$. We can then use the chain rule to find expressions of the derivatives of P in terms of x :

$$\frac{dP}{d\theta} = \frac{dP}{dx} \frac{dx}{d\theta} = -\sin \theta \frac{dP}{dx} \tag{8.9}$$

and

$$\frac{d^2 P}{d\theta^2} = \frac{d}{d\theta} \left[\frac{dP}{d\theta} \right] = \frac{d}{d\theta} \left[-\sin\theta \frac{dP}{dx} \right] = \sin^2\theta \frac{d^2 P}{dx^2} - \cos\theta \frac{dP}{dx}. \quad (8.10)$$

Substituting (8.9) and (8.10) into (8.8) then gives us

$$\sin^2\theta \frac{d^2 P}{dx^2} - 2\cos\theta \frac{dP}{dx} + \lambda P = 0. \quad (8.11)$$

Rewriting (8.11) in terms of x leads to

$$(1-x^2) \frac{d^2 P}{dx^2} - 2x \frac{dP}{dx} + \omega(\omega+1)P = 0 \quad (8.12)$$

where $\lambda = \omega(\omega+1)$ (note that both λ and ω may be complex valued). We recognise (8.12) as the general form of the Legendre equation with order 0 [46]. The solutions of (8.12) produces Legendre functions of the first and second kind:

$$P_\omega(x) = F\left(-\omega, \omega+1; 1; \frac{1-x}{2}\right) \quad \text{for } |1-x| < 2 \quad (8.13)$$

and

$$Q_\omega(x) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(\lambda+1)}{(2x)^{\lambda+1}\Gamma(\lambda+\frac{3}{2})} F\left(\frac{\lambda+1}{2}, \frac{\lambda+2}{2}; \lambda+\frac{3}{2}; \frac{1}{x^2}\right) \quad \text{for } |x| > 1 \quad (8.14)$$

where F is the hypergeometric series given by

$$F(a, b; c; x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_n (b)_n x^n}{(c)_n n!} = 1 + \frac{abx}{c} + \frac{a(a+1)b(b+1)x^2}{c(c+1)2} + \dots \quad (8.15)$$

and Γ is the gamma function given by

$$\Gamma(\lambda) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{\lambda-1} e^{-t} dt \quad \text{for } \Re(\lambda) > 0. \quad (8.16)$$

It turns out that Legendre functions of the second kind, $Q_\omega(x)$, diverge for all x and that the Legendre functions of the first kind, $P_\omega(x)$, only converge on $|x| < 1$ (our required domain) if ω is a non-negative integer [53]. If we restrict our attention to non-negative integer values of ω , then we see that P_ω actually takes the form of a polynomial given by

$$P_\omega(x) = \frac{1}{2^\omega \omega!} \frac{d^\omega}{dx^\omega} [(x^2-1)^\omega]. \quad (8.17)$$

The expression for P_ω for these first few values of ω is given in Table 3. In order to determine which value of ω (and therefore P_ω) satisfies our system, we have to re-examine our boundary conditions. In terms of P_ω and x , the Dirichlet boundary condition leads to $P_\omega(x=0) = 0$ and the Neumann Boundary condition leads to $\frac{dR}{dr'}|_{r'=1} P_\omega(x) = \mu x$. Since R (and therefore $\frac{dR}{dr'}|_{r'=1}$) is a function

Table 3: The first 5 Legendre Polynomials

ω	$P_\omega(x)$
0	1
1	x
2	$\frac{1}{2}(3x^2 - 1)$
3	$\frac{1}{2}(5x^3 - 3x)$
4	$\frac{1}{8}(35x^4 - 30x^2 + 3)$
5	$\frac{1}{8}(63x^5 - 70x^3 + 15x)$

of r' only, we must have that $P_\omega(x) = x$. If we cross reference this in table 3, we see that the corresponding value of ω is 1 and so the solution to (8.12) which satisfies the boundary conditions is $P = P_1(x) = x$ with $\omega = 1$. In terms of Θ , θ and λ , we have that $\Theta = \cos \theta$ with $\lambda = 2$.

We can now use this alongside the LHS of (8.6) (which was equal to λ) to get the following expression for R :

$$2r' \frac{dR}{dr'} + r'^2 \frac{d^2 R}{dr'^2} - 2R = 0. \quad (8.18)$$

This ODE has the form of an Euler equation and so R takes the form:

$$R = \alpha r' + \frac{\beta}{r'^2} \quad (8.19)$$

where α and β are constants [7]. In (8.3) we included the additional boundary condition that C' remains finite. $\Theta = \cos \theta$ and so $\Theta \leq 1$. This means that R must also remain finite and so β must be 0 (since 0 is in the domain of R). We then have that $R = \alpha r'$. The Neumann boundary condition in (8.3) leads to

$$\frac{dR}{dr'} = \alpha = \mu \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_N. \quad (8.20)$$

So, $R = \mu r'$. Putting our expressions for R and Θ into (8.4),

$$C' = \mu r' \cos \theta. \quad (8.21)$$

Rewriting (8.21) in dimensional variables gives the vector field for the concentration of Ca^{2+} :

$$C = \frac{q_0}{D} r \cos \theta + C_0. \quad (8.22)$$

The interpretation of this solution is relatively simple. Referring back to Figure 21 we can see that $r \cos \theta$ is the height above the $x - y$ plane in the positive z direction. This means that we expect the Ca^{2+} concentration to be the same at a given height, i.e. contours of calcium concentration will form horizontal bands. Furthermore, the concentration would increase linearly with an increase

in height. Recalling that Ca^{2+} promote vesicle fusion to the cell membrane, we would expect the rate at which new cell wall material is added (through vesicle exocytosis) to be greatest at the very apex of the tip. This would explain how the tip keeps its shape during growth.

Figure 22: (a) Plot of (8.22) with $D = 10^{-9}m^2s^{-1}$, $q_0 = 1.5 \times 10^{-9}nMm^2s^{-1}$ and $C_0 = 500nM$. (b) Here, a pollen tube has been injected with Fura-2-dextran, which allows the imaging of the free Ca^{2+} throughout the cell. This image has been reproduced from [24]. (c) An enlargement of the tip in (b) with a geometric and concentration scale.

A useful way of testing the validity of our model is to compare it with some relevant data. Hepler ran an experiment where he was able to measure the distribution of Ca^{2+} concentration in the tip of the pollen tube [25] (see Figure 22(c)). In order to make a useful comparison we have to match some of the relevant parameters. The concentration at the apical fringe was approximated to be $500nM$ and q_0 was determined by considering the maximal concentration in the tip ($\approx 1500nM$). This lead to $q_0 = 1.5 \times 10^{-9}nMm^2s^{-1}$. We can then plot (8.22) with $D = 10^{-9}m^2s^{-1}$, $q_0 = 1.5 \times 10^{-9}nMm^2s^{-1}$ and $C_0 = 500nM$ (see Figure 22(a)). One of the major drawbacks of our model is how the boundary conditions were chosen. While they do reflect some external observations such as calcium channel activity and a constant radius in the shank, their selection was such that a simple solution was achievable. Despite this, we can see that

our model matches the data collected by Hepler quite well and that the concentration of Ca^{2+} do indeed appear to roughly stagger linearly in horizontal bands. This justifies our use of this model as platform to build more complex models.

Influence of Electric Fields As was shown in section 2.1.2, the presence of a magnetic field had a statistically significant effect on the growth direction of pollen tubes. We will investigate how electromagnetic fields can effect growth directions by introducing an electric field to the problem formulation in (8.1) (see the previous closed system model section).

Introducing an electric field to our system will affect the governing dynamics within the cell as well as the way in which molecules are passed into the cell. For simplicity, we will consider the limiting case where only the mechanism through which molecules are passed into the cell is affected. Therefore, the problem formulation will be similar to last time but with different boundary conditions.

The Neumann boundary condition must include the effect of an electric field, \mathbf{e} say, placed in the system acting in a general direction (θ_0, ϕ_0) (see Figure 23). Notice that we can simply reorientate our system such that $\phi_0 = 0$, this means that the direction of the electric field is parameterised by θ_0 only. Last time we used the observation that forcing agents, in the form of calcium channels, were most active at the apex of the tip to form the Neumann boundary condition, $\frac{\partial C}{\partial r} \propto \cos \theta$ on $\partial\Omega_N$. The formulation of this Neumann boundary condition can be generalised to $\frac{\partial C}{\partial \mathbf{n}} \propto \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{n}$ on $\partial\Omega_N$ where \mathbf{F} is a forcing agent taking Ca^{2+} across the cell wall and \mathbf{n} is the unit vector pointing outwardly normal to the Neumann boundary (see Figure 23). The Neumann boundary conditions formulated by Dvoriashyna when modelling solute transport across retinal pigments also satisfy our generalisation so we can continue with some degree of confidence in our formulation [15]. Since our Neumann boundary is a hemisphere, $\frac{\partial C}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = \frac{\partial C}{\partial r}$. As discussed in section 1.4.3, the force of an electric field

Figure 23: A schematic of the problem formulation for Ca^{2+} concentration in an electric field.

on the Ca^{2+} will be in the same direction as the electric field and will have a magnitude proportional to the strength of the field. This means that $\frac{\partial C}{\partial r} \propto \mathbf{e} \cdot \mathbf{n}$ on $\partial\Omega_N$. By considering the strength of the electric field on the calcium ions relative to the diffusion constant, q_E say, the Neumann boundary condition can be rewritten as $D\frac{\partial C}{\partial r} = q_E(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{e})$ on $\partial\Omega_N$. We will assume from hereon out, without loss of generality (WLG), that $q_E > 0$.

Finally, we notice that by incorporating an electric field at an angle $\theta_0 \neq 0$, we introduce an asymmetry to our system. Therefore, the condition that the concentration is the same everywhere on $\partial\Omega_D$ is unreasonable. Instead, we can say that the average concentration on $\partial\Omega_D$ is equal to some constant, C_0 say. We can formulate this Dirichlet boundary condition mathematically as $\frac{1}{A(\partial\Omega_D)} \int_{\partial\Omega_D} C dA = C_0$ where $A(\partial\Omega_D)$ is the area of the Dirichlet boundary and dA represents an infinitesimally small area unit on $\partial\Omega_D$. We can now combine our previous problem formulation (8.1) with these updated boundary conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \nabla^2 C = 0 \quad \text{on } \Omega, \\
& \frac{1}{A(\partial\Omega_D)} \int_{\partial\Omega_D} C dA = C_0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_D, \\
& D \frac{\partial C}{\partial r} = q_0 \cos \theta + q_E(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{e}) \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_N, \\
& 0 \leq C < \infty \quad \text{on } \Omega, \\
& \text{where } \partial\Omega_D = \{(r, \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r \leq r_0, \theta = \frac{\pi}{2}\}, \\
& \partial\Omega_N = \{(r, \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r \leq r_0, 0 \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}\}, \\
& \text{and } \Omega = \text{int}\{\partial\Omega_D \cup \partial\Omega_N\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{9.1}$$

Again, the natural thing to do next is to non-dimensionalise the problem. We do this by introducing the new variables C' and r' where $C = C_0(C'+1)$ and $r = r_0 r'$. The dimensionless variables C' and r' have the same interpretation as last time. After substituting C' and r' into (9.1), we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \nabla^2 C' = 0 \quad \text{on } \Omega, \\
& \int_{\partial\Omega_D} C' dA = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_D, \\
& \frac{\partial C'}{\partial r'} = \mu \cos \theta + \mu_E(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{e}) \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_N, \\
& -1 \leq C' < \infty \quad \text{on } \Omega, \\
& \text{where } \partial\Omega_D = \{(r', \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r' \leq 1, \theta = \frac{\pi}{2}\}, \\
& \partial\Omega_N = \{(r', \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r' \leq 1, 0 \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}\}, \\
& \text{and } \Omega = \text{int}\{\partial\Omega_D \cup \partial\Omega_N\}
\end{aligned} \tag{9.2}$$

where $\mu_E = \frac{r_0 q_E}{DC_0}$. From here, we could consider a separable Ansatz and proceed in a similar way to last time. However, we can spot that this formulation is very similar to that of (8.3) which we have already solved. To capitalise on this observation, we split our solution into 2 partial solutions. Namely, $C' = C'_1 + C'_2$ where C'_1 is governed by:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \nabla^2 C'_1 = 0 \quad \text{on } \Omega, \\
& \int_{\partial\Omega_D} C'_1 dA = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_D, \\
& \frac{\partial C'_1}{\partial r'} = \mu \cos \theta \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_N, \\
& -1 \leq C' < \infty \quad \text{on } \Omega, \\
& \text{where } \partial\Omega_D = \{(r', \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r' \leq 1, \theta = \frac{\pi}{2}\}, \\
& \partial\Omega_N = \{(r', \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r' \leq 1, 0 \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}\}, \\
& \text{and } \Omega = \text{int}\{\partial\Omega_D \cup \partial\Omega_N\}
\end{aligned} \tag{9.3}$$

and C'_2 is governed by:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \nabla^2 C'_2 = 0 \quad \text{on } \Omega, \\
& \int_{\partial\Omega_D} C'_2 dA = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_D, \\
& \frac{\partial C'_2}{\partial r'} = \mu_E(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{e}) \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_N, \\
& -1 \leq C' < \infty \quad \text{on } \Omega, \\
& \text{where } \partial\Omega_D = \{(r', \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r' \leq 1, \theta = \frac{\pi}{2}\}, \\
& \partial\Omega_N = \{(r', \theta, \phi) \mid 0 \leq r' \leq 1, 0 \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}\}, \\
& \text{and } \Omega = \text{int}\{\partial\Omega_D \cup \partial\Omega_N\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{9.4}$$

It should be noted that the Laplacian operator acts linearly, so, if $\nabla^2 C'_1 = 0$ and $\nabla^2 C'_2 = 0$ then $\nabla^2(C'_1 + C'_2) = \nabla^2(C'_1) + \nabla^2(C'_2) = 0$. Similarly, the Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions of C'_1 and C'_2 can be combined to form those of C' . We then notice that the formulation for C'_1 in (9.3) is identical to that of C' in (8.3) with the exception of the Dirichlet boundary condition. However, we can see that the Dirichlet boundary condition in (9.3) is actually a generalisation of the one in (8.3) and so the solution found from (8.3), $C' = \mu r' \cos \theta$, will also satisfy (9.3). Therefore, $C'_2 = \mu r' \cos \theta$.

We will solve (9.4) in a slightly unorthodox way: we will 'spot' the general form of our solution using the boundary conditions and then use our knowledge of the general solution of the Laplace equation to determine the remaining constants. The first step is to get a more explicit expression for \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{e} involving θ , ϕ and θ_0 . Remember, \mathbf{n} is the unit vector pointing outwardly normal to the surface of a hemisphere so $\mathbf{n} = [\sin \theta \cos \phi, \sin \theta \sin \phi, \cos \theta]^T$. Then, \mathbf{e} is the direction of the electric field parameterised by θ_0 (as $\phi_0 = 0$) so $\mathbf{e} = [\sin \theta_0, 0, \cos \theta_0]^T$. This means that $\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{e} = \sin \theta_0 \sin \theta \cos \phi + \cos \theta_0 \cos \theta$ and the Neumann boundary condition becomes $\frac{\partial C'_2}{\partial r'} = \mu_E (\sin \theta_0 \sin \theta \cos \phi + \cos \theta_0 \cos \theta)$ on $\partial\Omega_N$. Then,

$$C'_2 = R(r') \mu_E (\sin \theta_0 \sin \theta \cos \phi + \cos \theta_0 \cos \theta) + G(\theta, \phi) \quad (9.5)$$

where $R(r')$ and $G(\theta, \phi)$ are unknown functions (with $\frac{dR}{dr'} = 1$ on $\partial\Omega_N$). It is important to check that the expression found in (9.5) satisfies the Dirichlet boundary condition. Note that $C'_2 = R(r') \mu_E (\sin \theta_0 \sin \phi) + G(0, \phi)$ on $\partial\Omega_D$, so

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\partial\Omega_D} C'_2 dA &= \int_0^1 \int_0^{2\pi} R(r') \mu_E (\sin \theta_0 \cos \phi) r' d\phi dr' + \int_{\partial\Omega_D} G(0, \phi) dA \\ &= \int_0^1 R(r') \mu_E \sin \theta_0 r' [\sin \phi]_0^{2\pi} dr + \int_{\partial\Omega_D} G(0, \phi) dA \\ &= \int_0^1 R(r') \mu_E \sin \theta_0 r'(0) dr + \int_{\partial\Omega_D} G(0, \phi) dA \\ &= \int_{\partial\Omega_D} G(0, \phi) dA. \end{aligned} \quad (9.6)$$

Setting $G(\theta, \phi) = 0$ ensures that the Dirichlet boundary condition is satisfied and gives us a separable solution whose properties we have already studied.

We can now continue to find the form of $R(r')$. From the formulation of Ca^{2+} concentration in a closed system, we established that for a separable solution, the Laplace equation produces a differential equation of the form

$$r'^2 \frac{d^2 R}{dr'^2} + 2r' \frac{dR}{dr'} - \lambda R = 0 \quad (9.7)$$

where λ is an unknown constant. We then found that if $\lambda = \omega(\omega + 1)$, $R(r')$ takes the form

$$R(r') = A_\omega (r')^\omega + B_\omega (r')^{-(\omega+1)} \quad (9.8)$$

where A_ω and B_ω are constants and ω may, in principal, be complex. Notice that ω and $-(\omega + 1)$ cannot both be positive and so, WLG, we can assume that $\Re(-(\omega + 1)) < 0$ (and so $\Re(\omega) > -1$). Then, in order to prevent our solution from diverging, we can set $B_\omega = 0$. We also know that $\frac{dR}{dr'} = 1$ on $\partial\Omega_N$, so $A_\omega \omega = 1$. We therefore have that $C'_2 = \frac{\mu_E}{\omega} (r')^\omega (\sin \theta_0 \sin \theta \sin \phi + \cos \theta_0 \cos \theta)$. All that is left to do is ascertain the value of ω . We will do this by determining for what value of ω the Laplace equation, $\nabla^2 C'_2 = 0$, is satisfied.

Before we start, we will ease notation by introducing $K = \sin \theta_0 \sin \theta \sin \phi + \cos \theta_0 \cos \theta$. Remember that the Laplacian in spherical polar coordinates is given by:

$$\nabla^2 C'_2 = \frac{1}{(r')^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r'} \left((r')^2 \frac{\partial C'_2}{\partial r'} \right) + \frac{1}{(r')^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial C'_2}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{(r')^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 C'_2}{\partial \phi^2}. \quad (9.9)$$

Then, after plugging in our expression for C'_2 , we get

$$\nabla^2 C'_2 = \frac{(r')^{\omega-2} \mu_E}{\omega} \left[\omega(\omega - 1)K + 2\omega K - K + \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial K}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial \phi^2} \right]. \quad (9.10)$$

Although it might not be entirely obvious, $\frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial K}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial \phi^2} = -K$. This means we can take a factor of K out and we are left with

$$\nabla^2 C'_2 = \frac{(r')^{\omega-2} \mu_E K}{\omega} [\omega(\omega - 1) + 2\omega - 2]. \quad (9.11)$$

This means that $\nabla^2 C'_2 = 0$ if and only if $\omega(\omega - 1) + 2\omega - 2 = 0$. This quadratic has solutions $\omega = 1$ and $\omega = -2$. Since we have assumed that $\Re(\omega) > -1$, we can disregard $\omega = -2$ and keep $\omega = 1$. This means we now have a solution to (9.4),

$$C'_2 = \mu_E r' (\sin \theta_0 \sin \theta \cos \phi + \cos \theta_0 \cos \theta). \quad (9.12)$$

The solution to (9.2) is then given by:

$$C' = C'_1 + C'_2 = r' [\mu \cos \theta + \mu_E (\sin \theta_0 \sin \theta \cos \phi + \cos \theta_0 \cos \theta)]. \quad (9.13)$$

Redimensionalising gives the solution to (9.1),

$$C = C_0(C' + 1) = C_0 + \frac{r}{D} [q_0 \cos \theta + q_E (\sin \theta_0 \sin \theta \cos \phi + \cos \theta_0 \cos \theta)]. \quad (9.14)$$

The last thing we may want to do before interpreting our solution is to determine for which values of μ and μ_E our model can guarantee non-negative

concentrations in our domain. In terms of our dimensionless concentration, this is equivalent to $C' \geq -1$. So, a necessary condition is:

$$-1 \leq r' [\mu \cos \theta + \mu_E (\sin \theta_0 \sin \theta \cos \phi + \cos \theta_0 \cos \theta)] \quad (9.15)$$

for $0 \leq r' \leq 1$, $0 \leq \theta \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$, $0 \leq \theta_0 \leq \pi$, $0 \leq \phi \leq 2\pi$.

By considering the values which r' , ϕ , θ and θ_0 can take in turn, we see that the minimal value of the RHS of (9.15) is $-\mu_E$ (when $r' = 1$, $\phi = \pi$, $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$ and $\theta_0 = \pi$). Therefore, in order to guarantee a non-negative concentration in our domain, we must have that

$$\mu_E \leq 1. \quad (9.18)$$

Equivalently,

$$\frac{DC_0}{r_0} \geq qE. \quad (9.19)$$

This condition suggests that (9.14) is valid for all possible electric field directions as long as the electric field strength isn't too strong.

In order to interpret our results it would be helpful to visualise them. Unfortunately our concentration profile (9.14) varies in r , θ and ϕ making visualisation difficult. However we can still gain into our model by plotting the concentration profile and fixing one variable at a time. Fixing ϕ will give us a vertical cross section of the tip (see Figure 24). Since the electric field is in the plane $\phi = 0$, the choice of $\phi = 0$ will allow us to determine if there is any alignment with the electric field. In addition, as we are interested in the influence of electric fields, it makes sense to introduce the dimensionless variable $M = \frac{\mu_E}{\mu}$. This represents influence of an electric field on the uptake of Ca^{2+} relative to the calcium channels.

Figure 24: Plots of (9.13) at $\phi = 0$ for a variety of different M (relative influence of electric field) and θ_0 (direction of electric field).

Figure 24 shows plots of (9.13) controlling for ϕ and μ with varying values of M and θ_0 . These plots are representative of a constant calcium channel effect (μ) and a variable electric field (μ_E). We can see that the concentration gradient within the tip increases with the presence of an electric field. Furthermore, there is a clear alignment of the direction of steepest concentration increase with the electric field (the strength of the alignment increases with μ_E). Alternatively, we could also impose the condition that $\mu + \mu_E = 1$. Then, the combined influence of the electric field and calcium channels is kept constant. The alignment of the distribution with the electric field is clearer for this case (see Appendix 5.4).

Fixing θ gives a horizontal cross section of the concentration distribution (see Figure 25). To see which value of θ is useful to fix it is helpful to remind ourselves of the role of Ca^{2+} in pollen tube growth. Ca^{2+} are thought to inhibit the motile activity of myosin causing the vesicles (which they are attached to) to be released from the actin filaments [57]. Since large actin filaments extend only as far as the tip [9], a region of interest would be the apical fringe (the Dirichlet boundary). Fixing $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$ is therefore a good choice. Figure 24 shows plots of (9.13) controlling for θ and μ with varying values of M (relative influence of the electric field) and θ_0 . These plots indicate that the presence of an electric field increases the concentration gradient on the apical fringe. Importantly, the introduction of an electric field creates regions of very low Ca^{2+} concentration on the apical fringe. This would infer that the release of vesicles from the actin filaments is being suppressed here. On the other hand, there are also regions of very high Ca^{2+} concentration on the apical fringe. This could suggest that the vesicles here are

Figure 25: Plots of (9.13) at the Dirichlet boundary (apical fringe) for a variety of different M (relative influence of electric field) and θ_0 (direction of electric field).

being released from the actin earlier (further down the shank) which means there is a surplus of floating vesicles on this side. An asymmetry in the distribution of floating vesicles in the tip suggests that there are parts of the cell membrane that more vesicles fuse to and parts where less vesicles fuse to. If this were the case then we would expect one side of the tip to grow more than the other. Since the side of the apical fringe with higher Ca^{2+} concentrations corresponds to the direction of the electric field, this model suggests that pollen tubes will grow in the direction of the electric field.

The last variable that we can fix is r . Fixing r will give hemispherical cross section (see Figure 26). Similar to when we fixed ϕ , a suitable choice for r can be made by recalling the mechanisms in which Ca^{2+} effect growth. Ca^{2+} promote the exocytosis of transport vesicles [32], so, $r = r_0$ (the Neumann boundary) is a good choice. Figure 26 shows plots of (9.13) controlling for r and μ with varying values of M (relative influence of the electric field) and θ_0 . The plots in Figure 26 suggest that the presence of an electric field increases the gradient of Ca^{2+} concentration across the cell membrane with regions of very low concentration and regions of very high concentration. Regions of the cell membrane with low Ca^{2+} concentration will decrease the rate at which vesicles fuse to the cell membrane whereas regions with higher concentration will increase the rate of vesicle exocytosis. It seems that the regions of highest concentration of Ca^{2+} on the cell membrane correspond to the direction of the electric field. Therefore, the oriented growth towards the direction of the electric field that

Figure 26: Plots of (9.13) at the Neumann boundary (cell membrane) for a variety of different M (relative influence of electric field) and θ_0 (direction of electric field).

was proposed when considering the asymmetrical vesicle distribution in the tip will be exacerbated by the asymmetry of the Ca^{2+} concentration distribution on the cell membrane.

We can validate our proposition as the effect of electric fields on the orientation of pollen tubes has been tested. In [5], Geitmann investigated the effect of an electric field on the growth orientation of pollen tubes (see Figure 27). The pollen tubes were initially left to grow without the presence of an electric field. An electric field was then introduced perpendicular to the direction of growth. After 105 minutes the electric field was switched off. After a further 10 minutes, the electric field was switched back on but in the opposite direction. The evolution of growth (see Figure 27) matches our proposition that the growth of pollen tube orientates itself towards the direction of an electric field.

Similar to when we modelled the Ca^{2+} distribution in the closed system (without an electric field), the key limitations of our model for the response of the Ca^{2+} distribution to electric fields is the choice of boundary conditions. While they match basic observations and previously used approaches (such as the one by Dvoriashyna in [15]), their form was selected so that they result in simple solutions. The lack of theory in the formulation of the boundary conditions means our approach isn't particularly generalisable. One way of overcoming this is to consider perturbations of the boundary conditions as a result of electric fields. Despite this, our simple model can help in providing potential explanations to the directed growth of pollen tubes in electric fields.

Figure 27: Depiction of pollen tubes orientating their growth in the direction of an electric field. Reproduced from [5].

3 Discussion and Future Directions

When modelling the cytoplasmic streaming rates in the shank of the pollen tube we identified the movement of vesicles along actin bundles and pressure gradients within the shank as the main factors effecting fluid flow. The movement of vesicles along the actin bundles in the periphery and centre of the shank were used as boundary conditions. They represented forcing agents on the fluid in the form of sliding 'walls' and so our flow was only defined between the actin bundles. We made a number of assumptions about the geometry of the shank as well as the flow itself to get the velocity profile (7.10) (see section 2.2.1). The shape of the velocity profile was governed by 3 parameters: α , β and A .

The values of α and β could be computed directly from the boundary conditions as they represented the sliding walls. α represented the locations of the actin bundles and defined the domain over which the velocity profile was valid. It therefore had a minimal effect on the shape of the velocity profile. On the other hand, β represented the relative rates at which the walls were sliding and had a considerable effect on the shape of the velocity profile. We found that very small values of β resulted in irregular velocity profiles with singularities occurring at the centre of the pollen tube. This corresponds to the case where the sliding walls are moving at very different rates. This suggests that the pollen tube can regulate cytoplasmic streaming by altering the rates at which vesicles are delivered along the actin bundles.

The parameter A represented the pressure gradient running along the length of the shank and had to be computed by considering the volumetric flow rate along with the growth speed. The computation of A in this way made hinged on the assumption that the average flow rate could be approximated by the growth speed. This required the amount of water entering and leaving the pollen tube to be minimal. However, if the pressure was measured at different position along the shank, the resulting pressure gradient could be calculated and would be less subjective. A pressure gradient along the length of the shank would result in fluid being driven up or down the shank. Therefore, A played a large role in shaping the velocity profile. In addition, we found that as the magnitude of A increased, the velocity profile would become less and less regular creating a singularity at the centre of the pollen tube. It was therefore concluded that pollen tubes can regulate their cytoplasmic streaming rates through pressure.

The investigation into the effect of the parameters suggests that the sliding walls and pressure gradients work alongside one another to shape the velocity profile. Due to the differences in timescales between pressure regulation and structural reconfiguration, it was proposed that pressure regulation was the main way in which pollen tubes are able to manage their cytoplasmic stream-

ing rates. The simple analytical model that we produced was also compared with a more complex numerical model. On matching the parameters, the two models had very similar outputs for the cytoplasmic streaming in the shank. Cytoplasmic streaming is an essential component to modelling the transport of substrates in the shank. The model we have developed could be used with the molecular transport equations to gain insight into how solutes that effect growth (such as Ca^{2+} , K^+ and H^+) are transported through pollen tubes.

The vast array of simplifications employed to formulate our model mean that some of the mechanisms that effect cytoplasmic streaming have been ignored. In addition, our model is highly sensitive to its input parameters. Since acquiring the velocities of the vesicles on the central and peripheral actin bundles is a relatively difficult task, there will be some degree of uncertainty in these measurements. This variability is likely to be exacerbated in our model meaning our model may not be great for predicting precise velocity profiles.

The statistical significance of electromagnetic fields on the direction of pollen tube growth motivated the further study of how mechanisms associated with growth could be effected by electric fields. We started off by modelling the distribution of Ca^{2+} concentration in the tip of the pollen tube. When modelling the distribution, we assumed that the transport of Ca^{2+} in the tip was governed by the steady state isotropic diffusion equation. Observations of a tip directed growth and a constant radius in the shank led to the formulation of the boundary condition at the apical fringe. The boundary condition at the cell membrane used the known activity of calcium channels. The system was then solved to get the Ca^{2+} concentration profile (8.22) (see section 2.2.2). The model suggests that the concentration of Ca^{2+} within the tip increases linearly up the tip. Furthermore, as Ca^{2+} promote vesicle fusion to the cell membrane, we would expect the rate at which new cell wall material is added (through vesicle exocytosis) to be greatest at the very apex of the tip. This would explain how the tip keeps its shape during growth. The model was then compared with some data by matching the parameters introduced by the boundary conditions to features of the data. Despite the simplicity of the model, it was surprisingly consistent with the data which suggests that a linearly increasing concentration of Ca^{2+} in the tip is a decent approximation.

We then considered the effect of an electric field on the distribution of Ca^{2+} concentration. It was assumed that the electric field had a negligible effect on the transport of Ca^{2+} within the tip and so only the boundary conditions needed adjusting. The effect of an electric field on the boundary condition at the cell membrane was motivated by the Lorentz force. The adjustment made to the boundary condition at the apical fringe was largely done to allow for a simple solution. The steady isotropic diffusion equation was then solved again with the

adjusted boundary conditions to get the Ca^{2+} concentration profile (9.14) (see section 2.2.2). On plotting the the Ca^{2+} concentration profile, it seems that the concentration gradient aligns itself with the direction of the magnetic field. To investigate this further, we recalled that Ca^{2+} promote the exocytosis of vesicles as well as the release of the vesicles from the actin bundles.

Since the point where vesicles are released from the actin is in the vicinity of the apical fringe, we plotted the Ca^{2+} concentration there. We found that the electric field brought about regions of very low Ca^{2+} concentration as well as areas of very high Ca^{2+} concentration. It was noted that the areas of high concentration were aligned with the direction of the electric field. It was then hypothesised that the release of vesicles from the actin was suppressed in areas of low Ca^{2+} concentration and stimulated in areas of high concentration. This would result in a greater abundance of free vesicles on the side of the pollen tube where the electric field was directed. We would then expect there to be a greater rate of vesicle exocytosis on this side.

As the exocytosis of vesicles occurs at the cell membrane, we also plotted the Ca^{2+} concentration there. We found that the parts of the cell membrane with the highest concentration were those that corresponded to the electric field direction. Since the fusion of vesicle to the cell membrane is promoted by Ca^{2+} , the rate of vesicle exocytosis in the direction of the electric field would be the greatest. This means that the effect of the asymmetrical rate of vesicle exocytosis compounds the effect of asymmetrical vesicle release. If the direction of the electric field governs the areas in which the most cell wall material is added, then we would expect the most growth to occur in the direction of the electric field. This means that pollen tubes' orientation of growth towards the direction of an electric field can be attributed, at least in part, to the distribution of Ca^{2+} .

The main drawback with both the models for Ca^{2+} distribution is their formulation of boundary conditions. While the boundary conditions mildly reflect some observations at those boundaries, their justification is limited. This is because of the sheer lack of physical theory underpinning them. Since the solution to the steady state isotropic diffusion equation is particularly sensitive to the form of its boundary conditions, it is possible that the true concentration distribution differs considerably from the model output. This limits the predictive capacities of the concentration models. Despite this, the model output of the concentration distribution for the case with no electric field resembles the true distribution surprisingly well. In addition, our model infers that pollen tubes will orientate their growth in the direction of an electric field which matches observations. This result could have profound applications in agriculture especially. This is because certain crops are particularly reliant on insect pollinators who currently face habitat loss, increased pesticide use, diseases, parasites, and

climate change. Their effectiveness as pollinators is therefore seriously undermined which poses significant challenges to agricultural productivity and food security. While we are by no means aiming to diminish the importance of insect pollinators, it may be essential for global stability if we rely less heavily on them. This could potentially be accomplished by introducing electric fields directed vertically downwards. Pollen tubes would then align themselves with this field and are therefore more likely to grow downwards towards the ovules and fertilise the egg. The role Ca^{2+} play in orientating pollen tubes in electric fields could be pivotal in optimising this process.

4 Conclusion

We have investigated fluid flow in the shank of the tube and the response of the distribution of Ca^{2+} in the tip to electric fields. The model we developed for cytoplasmic streaming in the shank illustrated the combined role of vesicles and pressure in shaping the velocity profile. We then went on to establish that flow regulation is primarily controlled by pressure. It was also shown that the directed growth of pollen tubes could, in part, be attributed to the response of Ca^{2+} to the electric field. It was hypothesised that the change in growth direction was due to an asymmetrical release of vesicles from the actin compounded by an asymmetrical rate of vesicle fusion to cell membrane.

While our results do provide us with a deeper understanding of pollen tube growth, there are still more refinements that can be made to our existing models to incorporate some of the features we ignored. When modelling calcium distribution in the tip of the cell in the presence of electromagnetic fields we may want to consider using numerical approaches such as finite element analysis which can handle more complex boundary conditions as well as governing dynamics with more terms. In addition, we may want to address more of the unexplained features of pollen tube growth. We found earlier that some of our results suggested that a magnetic field not only effects the growth direction of pollen tubes but may also be responsible for a greater variability in growth speeds. It is entirely unclear why this may be the case and more work needs to be done to understand what possible growth mechanisms may be responsible for the increased variability.

Pollen tubes play a key role in fertilising crops for consumption as well as maintaining diversity in ecosystems, facilitating ecological stability across the world. With climate changing threatening both agricultural reliability and environmental security, understanding the processes effecting pollen tube growth is more important than ever. While some of the results produced here illuminate us on how key factors effect growth and how they may interact, there are still

many features of pollen tube growth that may remain uncovered. A variety of mathematical approaches and tools are necessary to formulate reliable and efficient models as well as to validate any findings made.

5 Appendix

5.1 Solution to Logistic Growth

(1.1) can be solved by separating the variables:

$$\int \frac{1}{rL(1 - \frac{L}{K})} dL = \int dt$$

$$-\frac{K}{r} \int \frac{1}{L(L - K)} dL = \int dt$$

We can then perform partial fraction decomposition to get:

$$-\frac{K}{r} \int \frac{1}{K(L - K)} - \frac{1}{KL} dL = \int dt$$

Using the substitution $x = L - K$, leads to:

$$-\frac{\ln(\frac{K}{L} - 1)}{r} = t + C$$

Rearranging this gives:

$$L = \frac{K}{Ae^{-tr} + 1}$$

or alternatively:

$$L = \frac{K}{(\frac{K-L_0}{L_0})e^{-tr} + 1}$$

where L_0 is the initial length of the cell.

5.2 Solution to Logistic Growth

Equation 1.5 can be easily differentiated (this method reverse-engineers the problem but it is sufficient to demonstrate the relationship) using the chain rule. If $L = Ke^{-be^{-rt}}$ then define

$$u = -be^{-rt}.$$

Rewriting L in terms of u then gives

$$L = Ke^u$$

which can itself be rearranged to get

$$u = \ln\left(\frac{L}{K}\right).$$

L can also be differentiated:

$$\frac{dL}{du} = Ke^u = L.$$

Differentiating u with respect to t provides us with:

$$\frac{du}{dt} = rbe^{-rt} = -ru = -r \ln\left(\frac{L}{K}\right) = r \ln\left(\frac{K}{L}\right).$$

Then, by the chain rule,

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \frac{dL}{du} \frac{du}{dt} = r \ln\left(\frac{K}{L}\right) L,$$

as required.

5.3 Output of Hypothesis Tests Comparing Distributions of Growth Directions

The output of the first hypothesis test (control sample vs. uniform) is:

```
1 Reject =  
2 0  
3 p_value = 0.0663  
4 kstatistic = 0.1229  
5 critical_value = 0.1279
```

The output of the second hypothesis test (magnet sample vs. uniform) is:

```
1 Reject =  
2 1  
3 p_value = 2.0125e-12  
4 kstatistic = 0.2913  
5 critical_value = 0.1063
```

The output of the final hypothesis test (control sample vs. magnet sample) is:

```
1 Reject =  
2 1  
3 p_value = 1.6845e-07  
4 kstatistic = 0.3477
```

5.4 Additional Plots of the Distribution of Ca^{2+} Concentrations in Electric Fields

Figure 28: Plots of (9.13) at $\phi = 0$ for a variety of different M (relative influence of electric field) and θ_0 (direction of electric field). The additional constraint is imposed where $\mu + \mu_E = 1$.

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